

D5.2

Interim report on methods for generating hazard event sets and quantifying risk

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D5.2/Interim report on methods for generating hazard event sets and quantifying risk

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Abstract

Deliverable 5.2 of the MYRIAD-EU project, an interim report, aims to address the development of European-scale multi-hazard and multi-risk scenarios. The main objective of this deliverable is to integrate and enhance existing methodologies for assessing various natural and human-made hazards for use within the MYRIAD-EU framework. A detailed discussion on the components necessary for crafting European scale multi-risk scenario models is presented including a literature review. This includes an exploration of multi-sector risks at the European level, detailing the requirements for selected sectors within MYRIAD-EU. The report addresses the challenges in generating comprehensive multi-hazard and multi-risk scenarios, emphasising the need for robust, integrated methodologies.

Substantial effort is dedicated to the development of exposure metrics, covering aspects like population, buildings, infrastructure, agriculture, land cover, economic flows, and tourism. These metrics are crucial for assessing the potential impact of various hazards, such as earthquakes, tsunamis, wind, floods, landslides, tornadoes, hail, droughts, wildfires, and other climatic, hydrological, and geophysical threats. The report also explores biological hazards (vector-borne disease from mosquitoes and Covid-19), underscoring the diverse nature of risks faced by Europe where probabilistic, stochastic, and single events are required and have been extracted for the European context.

The extension of individual hazard data to multi-hazard frameworks is discussed, along with the development of vulnerability and fragility data for direct and indirect risk scenarios. This section paves the way for the application of these models in case study-specific scenarios, particularly for the MYRIAD-EU pilots.

The report examines the development of direct and indirect hazard and risk methodologies, showcasing a variety of approaches, including agent-based models, dynamic adaptive policy pathways, computational general equilibrium models, empirical and machine learning methods, and qualitative descriptions. The comparison of these approaches provides a comprehensive view of the direct and indirect risk modelling landscape. In conclusion, the report outlines the next steps for the integration of the WP5 risk scenarios into the project, setting the stage for continued development and implementation of multi-hazard and multi-risk scenarios across Europe.

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- Public
- Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
- Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the European Commission Services)
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1 Purpose of the Deliverable and Introduction

1.1 Objective

This deliverable aims to provide the base tools and methods for the production of European multi-hazard and multi-risk scenarios as part of WP5, with a focus on their applicability to five case study regions (pilots) within Europe. It is structured to give the datasets and interim models used within the sector-specific analyses at European scale and within the pilots.

The document begins with a short literature review, establishing the current state of knowledge and methodologies within the context of multi-hazard and multi-risk scenarios in Europe, as well as referring to existing literature reviews and other parts of the MYRIAD-EU project where background knowledge related to this deliverable can be found.

The core of the deliverable describes the development of multi-risk scenario modelling at a European scale including most importantly a consistent and state-of-art baseline for risk from the 3 components of hazard, vulnerability and exposure. It defines the needs for sectors chosen within the MYRIAD-EU project and develops exposure metrics for various elements such as population, buildings, infrastructure, agriculture, economic flows, and tourism. This section also details the development of methodologies for direct and indirect hazard and risk assessment, thereby contributing to the understanding of both individual and integrated hazard scenarios.

With MYRIAD-EU, case studies (Pilots) will be used to apply the developed methodologies to specific scenarios. This will include the development of direct hazard and risk methodologies and datasets for the pilots. The application of empirical, probabilistic, and stochastic models is discussed, including both independent and dependent risk scenarios. Additionally, section 4.4 contrasts different modelling approaches, such as agent-based models, policy pathways, and economic models, providing a nuanced understanding of their applicability and performance.

The document further explores sector-specific multi-risk scenario modelling, providing insights tailored to particular areas of interest. It also extends the analysis to spatiotemporal dimensions, including the consideration of future scenarios, which is crucial for long-term planning and risk mitigation.

Finally, the deliverable discusses the integration of these models and methodologies into the workflow of the MYRIAD-EU project as detailed in Figure 1, outlining the next steps. This integration is key to ensuring that the findings are actionable and can effectively contribute to risk management and decision-making processes.

Overall, the deliverable is designed to advance the understanding of multi-hazard and multi-risk scenarios in Europe and to provide the necessary tools and analyses to manage these risks effectively, specifically tailored to the needs of the MYRIAD-EU project.

Figure 1: Overview of the workflow of the MYRIAD-EU project. T5.2 and T5.3 are crucial to the entire workflow of the project.

2 Literature Review on European Multi-hazard and Multi-risk Scenarios specific to MYRIAD-EU

2.1 Introduction

As part of WP1, the state of art of multi-hazard and multi-risk definitions, as well as a compendium of models and datasets were reviewed. A common baseline was developed and understanding on multi-hazard and multi-risk definitions, indicators, functions, methods, tools, and policies was put together in the handbook of multi-hazard risk definitions and indicators (Gill et al., 2022), and a WIKI-style platform - Disaster Risk Gateway - showcasing existing methods and tools, and an overview of multi-hazard risk management policies was produced (Schlumberger et al., 2023). These serve to facilitate a consensus of understanding within and outside the project.

There have been many attempts to characterise natural and human-made hazards over time (NARSIS-EU WP1.1 (2018)), thus these will not be repeated here. However, focussing on newer studies, these include the IRDR-DATA project, Gill et al. (2014), ASAMPSE (2017), and more recently the UNDRR Hazard Definition and Classification Review. This was then updated by the Hazard Information Profiles including 302 different hazards released in 2021 (UNDRR, 2021). The list of hazards to be characterised within the project were proposed as part of the project scope (flood, drought, extreme wind, earthquake, heat, storms, thunder/hail, tsunami, snow, volcanic eruptions, fire, tornado, biological hazards and landslides) via interactions with the pilots and within the planning phase, given the huge amount of potential hazards, however further discussions have shown changes, such as including tornado in many environments.

The definition of individual hazards is important as the various triggering, consecutive and other states of combinations of hazards are important in order to quantify the hazard metric for use in vulnerability functions moving through to risk of the exposed assets.

The basic model components are as usual hazard, exposure, vulnerability of any exposed elements transferring through to risk as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of damage/risk assessments.

There are a number of different hazard types that are relevant to pilots and sectors. One is a single event scenario. One can imagine this as a single archery board where the largest hazard is in the middle, with diminishing hazard values moving away from the centre. This is useful for showing the example of a single event as seen in Figure 3. However, sometimes, one wants to know the maximum possible impact at any location, as for that single event, the impact may be low, but for a different single event at a nearby location this may cause significant damages. For example, when looking at a time period of 10,000 years of all possible events (a stochastic event set – right in Figure 3) that can occur in terms of magnitude and location, then we can start to see the possible impacts for a region and how often a certain economic damage and loss will occur for a certain return period, or how many events may exceed a damage value of 10 million Euros in a certain

sector. There is another type of output, which is called a probabilistic map (middle in Figure 3), where the combination of the events is made for a certain return period i.e. the 10,000-year map shows the maximum intensity from any event at each point. This type of output can be useful for certain hazard outputs, however, is less useful for risk, as the events are not able to be disentangled from one another, meaning any damage metric has little meaning without being able to identify the individual events.

Figure 3: Schematic representation of single event (and probabilistic maps and stochastic event sets).

There are a number of existing software tools that have the ability to handle multi-hazard modelling (interactions between single hazards rather than only independent modelling) such as HAZUS (used extensively in the US/Canada), RiskScape (used extensively in the Pacific), Climada (Stalhandske et al., 2023), RIESGOS and a few others with differing levels of multi-hazard interactions. Depending on the nature of the hazards, then these tools are able to be used in combination with each other. These, however, will be further discussed in the final report and not in this interim report, and multi-hazard scenarios and risk outputs will be produced for the software.

EU Projects such as RAIN and PRIMAVERA have previously characterised multiple hazards as well as integrated risks inform the starting point for multi-hazard modelling. These are detailed within Gill et al. (2022) and ongoing lists will be available in the Disaster Risk Gateway. There are a number of ongoing projects in addition such as Paratus, MEDiate, MIRACA, C2IMPRESS, KNOWING and The HuTand others, which need to be audited in an ongoing manner during MYRIAD-EU in order to ensure compatibility and complementarity.

The useful datasets from previous studies include the WISC, STORM and PRIMAVERA datasets for wind-based hazards; JRC, GLOFRIS, FATHOM for floods; SERA and SHARE for earthquake; and other projects which provide datasets (both stochastic and historic for these disaster types). Some of the sets originally to be examined are detailed in Table 1 and the final produced and downloaded sets are shown in this documents.

Table 1: Examples of single hazard datasets that can be used for the generation of multi-hazard events from the grant agreement.

Hazard class	Examples of datasets and models
Meteorological/ Climatological	Wind: Copernicus WISC ¹⁹ , STORM ²⁰ ; Hail: European Severe Weather Database ²¹ , Potential Hail Index ²² , Stochastic event catalog ²³ ; Drought: European Drought Observatory database ²⁴ , CHIRPS ²⁵ ; Extreme temperature: E-OBS ²⁶ , Climate Extreme Indices ²⁷ ; Wildfire: European Fire Database ²⁸ ; Storm surge and coastal flooding: GTSR ²⁹ ; Climate change: ECA-D, CORDEX, CMIP6, CMIP5, Station Data trends.
Hydrological	River Flood: National Hazard Maps, LISFLOOD-EU ³⁰ , GLOFRIS ³¹ ; Coastal flood: JRC coastal hazard maps ³² ; Mass movement: Global Landslide Catalogue ³³ ; European landslide susceptibility map ³⁴ .
Geological	Earthquake: SERA, SHARE ³⁵ , CATDAT ³⁶ , National Models (e.g. GFZ, INGV), GEM ³⁷ ; Tsunami: TSUMAPS-NEAM, Tsupy ³⁸ , GTM; Volcanic activity: GVP ³⁹ , VOGRIPA ⁴⁰ .
Biological	Pests: FAO's Locust watch ⁴¹ , EPPO global pests database ⁴² ; Diseases: WHO-Europe's CISID infectious diseases database ⁴³ , WHO's various databases on epidemiological trends ⁴⁴ ; Vegetation: FLUXCOM ⁴⁵ , GOME2 SIF ⁴⁶ , GIMMS NDVI ⁴⁷ .

2.2 A multi-hazard context with a focus on methods and tools

The following provides an overview of the evolution of multi-hazard assessment methodologies within the European Union and highlights key contributions from past projects and research efforts. An in-depth review of past projects and methodologies developed within the European Union to address multi-hazard scenarios has been made in the FP7 MATRIX project, in the EURATOM NARSIS Project and in this project in Deliverable 1.2 and the definitions within the Disaster Risk Gateway. Thus, only a brief introduction to the main multi-hazard methods is described here.

The foundation or starting point for European scale multi-hazard assessment was created by the integration of hazard and vulnerability components into a unified index was developed by Granger and Jones (2000), setting the stage for subsequent research favouring integrated approaches. MunichRe (2003) and Thierry et al. (2008) expanded on these concepts by aggregating hazards over defined spatial and temporal domains, marking a trend towards comprehensive risk assessment methodologies.

The narrative also explores specific methodologies and tools developed for multi-hazard assessments. Nicholls et al. (1999) and Hinkel et al. (2014) investigated the impact of hazard combinations, with particular relevance to nuclear power plants. Dietrich et al. (2010) employed a coupled model to analyse interactions between various hazards, encompassing riverine floods, wind, storm surges, tidal effects, and wind wave effects. Cavalieri et al. (2015) advanced Object-Oriented Framework for Infrastructure Modelling and Simulation (OOFIMS) for multi-hazard scenarios, including earthquakes and floods.

Further multi-hazard bases were laid by Kappes (2012) and Mignan et al. (2014), who conducted quantitative analyses of how different hazards interact, establishing critical approaches to this complex field. Their work emphasised the need to consider the interplay between hazards, a principle echoed by Marzocchi et al. (2012), who critiqued hazard models for their limitations in addressing interconnected risks, advocating for integrated risk assessment frameworks.

The MATRIX Project (2010-2013) introduced a 3-Level Approach (L1, L2, and L3) for multi-risk assessment frameworks, which forms a critical component of this narrative. This approach encompasses the definition of a space/time assessment window and a risk metric for quantifying expected losses. It also involves the identification of threats, including various natural hazards like earthquakes, floods, and landslides. Single hazard assessments cover rate of occurrence, pathway, and intensity measures. Vulnerability assessments address elements at risk, including human populations and buildings, while consequences are evaluated in terms of chosen metrics, such as loss of life, economic losses, or environmental degradation. This comprehensive approach represents a significant step forward in advancing multi-hazard assessment methodologies within the European Union.

Further, various methodologies are compared here for their efficacy in modelling complex multi-hazard scenarios:

Markov Chain (MC) and Dynamic Bayesian Network (DBN) methods for risk assessment were examined in RAIN, ASAMPSA-E and MATRIX and extended within the NARSIS project from 2017-2021 as part of EURATOM (Gehl et al., 2024; Rohmer and Gehl, 2020; Mohan et al., 2020). The most important aspect of multi-hazard modelling in NARSIS which focussed on nuclear power plants was on the topic of duration of hazards as this influences the overlapping and interaction nature of multi-hazard events. A novel method developed within the RAIN project utilises Bayesian probability theory and a probability sort algorithm to model time-dependent, inhomogeneous, and cascading effects over time and space.

The detailed implementation of these methodologies and their integration into multi-hazard research is provided by van Erp (2017), offering a comprehensive approach to understanding and managing the complex nature of multi-hazard scenarios within the EU context.

In addition to these methodologies, Gill and Malamud (2014) for their classification of hazard interactions and Zaghi et al. (2016) for their framework identify hazard interactions through both the nature of hazards (Level I interactions) and the effects of hazards (Level II interactions). This framework is noted to align well with NARSIS, which integrated this into their work, and took into account the interactions of multiple hazards occurring simultaneously, which is often overlooked in building codes.

When moving to the classification of multi-hazard models, there are numerous methods as classified by Tilloy et al. (2019) and further within the first phase of MYRIAD-EU, however this schematic helps classify the three main types of models: Stochastic; Empirical and Mechanical in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Schematic representation of model types for multi-hazard and risk modelling.

Depending on the different hazard models employed, the interaction of the hazards can be looked at with station data and using copulas to explain the interactions between two hazard metrics (either empirical or stochastic); or other multivariate models may be employed.

In the absence of data, or in complex situations, a mechanical model may be required (these are also known as physical models which are often seen in meteorology or geophysics).

In other instances, single hazard data from empirical data can be used; and then the interactions need to be looked at through other methods. Even when focussing on a single hazard, these can of course be classified into the same framework.

2.3 Existing Work within MYRIAD-EU which interacts with WP5

Interactions with the other WPs (shown in Table 2)

WP1 (Diagnosis and State-of-the-Art): The datasets and methods developed for generating multi-hazard event sets in WP5 are informed by the findings and data collected in WP1. The diagnostic work in WP1 lays the foundation for understanding the current state of knowledge and data availability, which is then expanded upon in WP5 for the development of realistic multi-hazard scenarios.

WP2 (Framework and Guidance Protocols): The framework and methodology developed in WP2 influences WP5's tools and methods for hazard event sets and risk quantification.

WP3 (Pilot Studies and Stakeholder Engagement): The development of tools and methods in WP5 is driven by the requirements of the pilot core user groups and stakeholders through the iterative process described in WP3. This collaborative approach ensures that the tools and methods developed are aligned with the practical needs and insights gained from the pilot stakeholders.

WP4 (Risk Drivers and Dynamic Feedbacks): Risklayer's work in WP5 is directly influenced by the developments in WP4, which focuses on identifying and understanding the dynamic feedbacks between risk drivers. The empirical evidence and functions developed in WP4 are crucial for WP5, particularly in Task 5.2, where Risklayer incorporates these dynamics and feedbacks into risk quantification models.

WP6 (Disaster Risk Management Pathways Framework): The outcomes and risk scenarios developed by Risklayer in WP5 can inform WP6, such as the identification of threshold events to be incorporated into Disaster Risk Management (DRM) pathways for those pilot regions following the Dynamic Adaptive Policy Pathways – Multi-Risk (DAPP-MR) approach.

Table 2: Existing work which interacts with WP5.

Work Package	Work Description	Key Referenced Documents
WP1	Diagnosis and Data Collection	WIKI-style online crowdsourcing platform of multi-hazard, multi-risk methods, models, and tools (D1.1) Handbook of multi-hazard, multi-risk concepts, definitions, and indicators (D1.2)
WP2	Framework and Guidance Protocols	Initial framework and guidance protocol document (D2.1)
WP3	Pilot Studies and Stakeholder Engagement	Terms of reference for Pilot core user and stakeholder groups (D3.1) Interim report on implementation and testing of MYRIAD-EU methods and tools in each Pilot (D3.3a)
WP4	Risk Drivers and Dynamic Feedbacks	Report on Novel Methods for Detecting Empirical Evidence of Dynamics & Feedbacks of Risk Drivers (D4.3)
WP6	Disaster Risk Management Pathways	Interim report on collaborative systems and DAPP approaches to develop forward-looking DRM pathways (D6.3)

3 The components needed for European Scale Multi-risk Scenario Modelling

3.1 Background

3.1.1 Multi-sector Risk at the European Scale

The interconnectedness and interdependencies within and among different sectors can cause unanticipated cascading of system failures in the context of multi-risk scenario modelling. Furthermore, increasing complexity, new threats, and the vast range of interdependencies among different sectors in modern society gives rise to ever more complicated forms of risk. Therefore, in modelling multi-risk scenarios at the European scale, an integrated, consistent, and formal consideration to the question of resilience of different sectors from a systems and trans-disciplinary perspective is required.

Figure 5: Iconographic representation of the 6 study sectors.

To illustrate the multi-sectoral dynamics at play in MYRIAD-EU, it is essential to examine the interconnections and interdependencies among the various sectors it addresses as seen in Figure 5. These connections unveil a complex web of relationships across different sectors. For example, taking the perspective of the **tourism** sector, the reliance on the **energy** sector to power various facets such as accommodations, tourism attractions, food and beverage services, etc., can be highlighted. This reliance is further compounded by regulatory pressures and the growing imperative for the tourism industry to embrace climate-friendly practices, necessitating sustainability measures and a reduced carbon emissions footprint (Gössling et al., 2018).

Furthermore, **food and agriculture** assumes a critical role by supplying food and raw materials essential for the hospitality industry and various tourism services. Disruptions in food and agriculture by hazards such as extreme weather events, can significantly impact tourism by intricate supply chain links affecting the availability and quality of food offerings, potentially leading to tourist dissatisfaction and reduced visitor numbers (UNWTO, 2016 and WTO, 2018).

Finance provides essential funding for tourism-related initiatives such as hotel construction and tourism infrastructure development (UNWTO, 2020). **Infrastructure and transport** encompasses elements such as roads, airports, and utilities, which are of course pivotal to the tourism sector, as it ensures tourists have access to destinations and a comfortable stay (UNWTO, 2014).

Moreover, efficient transport systems become fundamental, underpinning tourists' mobility and serving as a cornerstone of the overall tourism experience (Crouch & Ritchie, 1999). These intricate sectoral connections emphasise the need for comprehensive and coordinated efforts within MYRIAD-EU to achieve actionable outcomes across multiple end-users and stakeholders. Table 3 provides a list of potential direct and indirect damage metrics that can be relevant to the sectors addressed in MYRIAD-EU as a lead into a larger list of risk metrics below in Chapter 4.

Table 3: List of MYRIAD-EU sectors and some key potential direct and indirect damage metrics.

Sector	Potential Direct and Indirect Damage Metrics
Finance	Investment & Built Stocks: Replacement, Reconstruction, Depreciated Cost, Reconstruction with International Laborers, Insurance Cost, Contents Included, Risk Layers
Infrastructure and Energy	Useability and Damage Analysis, Network Analysis
Agriculture	Crop, Land Use, Stock Dependent, Food
Tourism	Hotels, Interactions with Sectors, Population Metrics, Socioeconomic Information, Fatality & Disruption Functions
Ecosystems	Forest damage, Environmental metrics
Food Security	Food/Agriculture (Impact on Supply Chains and Critical Infrastructure)

Several EU research projects in addition to the multi-hazard ones above have developed concepts addressing multi-sectoral risk, mostly from a single-hazard perspective. For example, multi-sectoral resilience concepts in emBRACE; systemic earthquake vulnerability and risk analysis for energy, transport, infrastructure and health in SYNER-G; stress testing interconnected critical infrastructure systems in STREST; extreme weather impacts on Critical Infrastructure (CI) in INTACT and FLOODsite; interactive and participatory scenario planning for different sectoral end users in SENSUM and IMPRESSIONS; integrative, interdisciplinary governance models for emerging and existing risks in RISKBRIDGE, ADAM, MEDIATION, and CapHazNet; guideline development for managing disasters and emerging risks in INTEG-RISK; and building and sustaining stakeholder networks for CIP in CIPNet covering a multitude of CI sectors (<https://cordis.europa.eu/>).

3.1.2 What is needed for the sectors chosen within MYRIAD-EU?

MYRIAD-EU's vision is to employ a multi-sectoral, multi-risk, and systemic approach through forward-looking disaster risk management strategies that consider trade-offs and synergies across sectors, hazards, and scales. To realise this vision, a harmonised framework is being developed across five multi-hazard, multi-sector, and multi-scale Pilots, cataloguing feedback mechanisms between risk drivers.

In terms of the requirements for WP5, where comprehensive multi-risk scenarios need to be generated using software to produce metrics relevant for addressing the selected sectors, several important considerations are outlined in MS22 - Format of data requirements for risk models agreed between WP4-6 (Daniell et al., 2023). These considerations pertain to the requirements for different stochastic and probabilistic hazard data sets, as well as the format of risk metrics as outputs from risk models. These considerations include:

1. Developing a **catalogue of dynamic feedbacks** that exist between risk drivers across various sectors, by focusing on the pilots, which provide real-world context for understanding multi-sectoral interactions and interdependencies.
2. Establishing clear definitions of **key indicators** that are pertinent to each of the sectors. These indicators are essential for generating both quantitative and qualitative multi-hazard and multi-risk scenarios.
3. Defining **impact-relevant threshold parameters** that will be employed in the DRM solutions across the five different pilot projects, to the extent that these parameters will be produced through risk models developed in WP5.

These considerations are crucial for ensuring the successful execution of WP5 and the generation of comprehensive multi-risk scenarios that are relevant to the selected sectors.

3.1.3 Challenges in producing multi-hazard and multi-risk scenarios

Producing comprehensive multi-hazard and multi-risk scenarios entails a multitude of challenges both now and in the future. On the hazard front, crafting a plausible temporal sequence for interactions between various hazard drivers remains complex, as does accurately assigning return periods to events. Detailed modelling of events in which failure of infrastructure and buildings occurs is intricate work, and the dynamic nature of hazards means they may change over time incrementally, adding uncertainty. Moreover, establishing impact-relevant thresholds is challenging. In terms of vulnerability, predicting future changes and assessing the impact of recent volcanic events like La Palma and El Hierro on island vulnerability pose significant hurdles. Previous events also have lingering effects, but the lack of accurate vulnerability data further complicates assessments. Regarding exposure, obtaining precise time-of-day data to understand tourist patterns and adapting to changing demographic profiles are necessary but not always readily available. Additionally, quantifying the effectiveness of Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) measures requires navigating shifts in decision-making policies that influence risk acceptance, unravelling complex cause-and-effect relationships within impact chains, and managing the multitude of interactions between sectors and hazards.

3.2 Development of Exposure Metrics

Exposure metrics have been examined as part of the work at European scale and in the pilot regions. A focus has been placed on population, buildings and infrastructure datasets, as these are the datasets where vulnerability functions and most focus has been centred in previous studies, allowing for risk outputs to be produced at a European scale for some event types where this data exists.

An interface is being set up which will be released as part of D5.4, which will allow the user to see what is possible in terms of multi-risk and multi-hazard scenarios in which locations around Europe as well as which exposure data are available to fill the model.

The final deliverable will be filled with links to the final data at European and case study region scale. In addition, web links will be given for each source.

In addition, each of the sectors has been examined in order to output key metrics where possible and it is believed that they can be used to move through from hazard to risk. For tourism for example, outbound and inbound tourism expenditure as well as GDP have been explored, in addition to arrivals data.

Forward-looking models of some of the exposure metrics are included in the associated exposure tables in the Appendix. This is crucial as the exposure as well as hazard changes over time, thus, it is important to characterise this change for use within the direct risk models. Currently, the European scale direct models include a change for capital, GDP and population statically for futuristic years out to 2100 from various models, however, sector-specific models of hazard, exposure and vulnerability change are wanting to be built up in some of the pilot studies. This is currently being discussed within a few pilots: Canary Islands, Danube and Veneto.

3.2.1 Population

Population grids form an important basis for analysis of any socioeconomic effects in terms of risk scenarios. Population estimation on a European scale has been tackled by many groups, including GHSL, WSF, EUROSTAT, CIESIN, Landscan, Maddison (2008) and Tatem (2013-2023), on the basis of census and land use data (see Appendix A: Table 20).

Seasonal and temporal datasets also exist and are useful for fatality functions as well as population movements for Tourism, Transport, Food as well as biological hazards like COVID-19. The urban and rural distribution of population gives an insight into not only economic losses, but also the differences in height, style and quality of infrastructure typologies. Generally speaking, the ratio of capital stock to GDP reduces with higher percentages of rural typologies, which is important for economic costs of assets for all the sectors in MYRIAD-EU.

3.2.2 Buildings

For buildings, there are a number of key parameters that are required if possible. Number of buildings, typology, number of storeys, footprints, location, and cost are all key parameters. Census and economic establishment survey data often hold the following for residential urban and rural environments and also for non-residential environments on an urban setting:

- Walling types
- Roofing types
- Flooring types
- Household Size (no. of people)
- Labour Force Participation Rate (%)
- Storey heights
- Age of building stock
- No. of floors, rooms and buildings; and
- Building quality and building cost data

However, for other types of buildings these are often not present. A number of European building inventories exist, however, they are very location dependent. In essence depending on the use case, the hazard type and the location, very different building inventories may be needed, i.e. for hail: roof types and exterior data may be crucial, yet other parameters such as floor type less so. The GHS BUILT-C MSZ product is a satellite based product at 10m resolution giving the details of building height and classification as shown in Figure 6. See Appendix A: Table 20 for further datasets used in MYRIAD-EU.

Figure 6: Map of the spatial distribution of building morphologies based on the Global Human Settlement Layer “GHS-BUILT-C” dataset.

3.2.3 Infrastructure

As part of the infrastructure data for the WP5 risk scenarios, a collection of European scale data was required in order to derive the possible datasets for use as the exposure inputs to any holistic damage modelling.

Many datasets have been sourced for use where appropriate. The value of these assets has not been quantified in most cases, however the location, and type are often present in each dataset, allowing for derivation of cost depending on the pilot usage. These have been clipped to Europe where appropriate for use.

Datasets were collected encompassing road, railway, transport, power, water, telecommunications and other European scale datasets as shown in the Appendix A: Table 22.

3.2.4 Agriculture and Land Cover

Agriculture, food production and land cover data are important for use in risk scenarios where large damages may occur such as hail, floods and geophysical hazards such as volcanic eruptions. There are a number of datasets that have been extracted for use at a European or pilot scale within the project such as those shown in Figure 7.

In addition to global datasets, there are numerous continental- and country scale datasets that were developed and published in recent years as seen in Appendix A: Table 23.

Figure 7: Colour graded maps of GDP in agriculture (left) and fisheries (right).

3.2.5 European scale economic flow datasets

There are a number of global GDP datasets available that can give insights into the outputs and expenditures within different subsections of the economy.

For sectoral analysis in MYRIAD-EU, it was crucial to collect these and the level at which they were produced in order to give a common baseline for the risk scenarios, as well as allow for input-output style models to connect the pilots and enable Europe wide risk scenarios (a table of all datasets will be provided for final deliverable); this will include: Subnational GDP dataset 1: EU-KLEMS (NUTS3, I-O), Subnational GDP dataset 2: Blackenspoor, Subnational GDP dataset 3: CATDAT, Subnational GDP dataset 4: EUROSTAT, G-ECON dataset (1990-2005, 1km), DOSE – GDP (1960-2020, subnational), HANZE – GDP (1870-2020, 100m), ARDECO NUTS2 I-O, etc.).

3.2.6 Tourism

For the tourism sector, an extensive effort has been made to extract datasets relevant to tourism, in line with the findings of the “risk metric” workshop made as part of WP5.

A code was made in order to aggregate all data from EUROSTAT at either NUTS2 or NUTS3 level despite issues with the NUTS code depending on the location and when the NUTS code was produced (there have been numerous versions over the last 15 years). These have been provided as geopackages with the data with an example shown in Figure 8.

Tourism GDP, GDP aggregates from the economic flow datasets, tourism density, Tourism Differences over time have been some of the datasets produced for the tourism sector as part of this study. This allows for such outputs like movement in population to the coastlines in August in Italy and the Adriatic or Balaton, Hungary showing the difference in population from August vs. November using the ENACT data as an indicator as for seasonal tourism.

In addition, tourism data derived from OpenStreetMap (OSM) for Europe including hotels, restaurants and other tourist landmarks have been produced, as well as comparisons of international tourism expenditure and domestic tourism expenditure.

Figure 8: An example of the European tourism indicators that were prepared for use on NUTS2 and NUTS3 from EUROSTAT.

3.3 Development of Direct Hazard and Risk Methodologies and Event sets

Daniell et al. (2023) included the production of stochastic and probabilistic datasets for different hazards. These were either sourced from existing projects or produced through our own metrics and runs. In all cases these have been adapted to ensure compatibility with the zones of our pilots where possible.

The European scale metrics therefore were sourced to cover all of these hazard types and a few additional hazard types deemed important at European scale.

The event sets will be developed under current conditions and for future conditions under climate change where applicable using the future exposure via some of the forward looking studies explained in the table – i.e. either HANZE, HYDE, IIASA or some other global estimates for integrated socioeconomic Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) change. The time-horizon and selection of RCPs is being discussed within the pilots and will be integrated, however the future conditions are discussed in each of the following hazards where appropriate. Depending on the pedigree of the hazard models, some use CMIP5, CMIP6 and various other regional climate models.

Table 4: Overview of chosen hazard types in the 5 MYRIAD-EU Pilot regions.

	Veneto	North Sea	Scandinavia	Canary Islands	Danube

3.3.1 Earthquake and associated aftershock sequences

Earthquakes are a common hazard around Europe. , The chance of earthquake hazard is especially high in Southern Europe, including Italy, Greece, South-East-Europe and Turkey, as well as Iceland. Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Assessments (PSHA) are systematic and scientific approaches for evaluating the likelihood of earthquakes occurring in a specific geographic area over a given period. These assessments aim to quantify the seismic hazard by considering a range of potential earthquake scenarios, their probabilities, and associated ground shaking intensities.

These assessments involve collecting geological and seismological data, characterising potential seismic sources, estimating earthquake frequency and magnitude, predicting ground motion, and quantifying uncertainties associated with data and models. The outcome is a probabilistic model that integrates various earthquake scenarios, providing hazard curves that depict the likelihood of different levels of ground shaking over time. Critical at locations where risk analyses need to be undertaken are the geotechnical data, where employing Vs30 as a proxy is often necessary due to a lack of more detailed information. The Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) and spectral ordinates are calculated for each location across different return periods using the same modelling approach.

Over the last decades, several global and European seismic hazard models have been developed. The most commonly known and applied is the 2013 SHARE model (ESHM13), which has been renewed and updated within the SERA-EU project.

The 2020 European Seismic Hazard Model (ESHM20) (Danciu et al. 2020) was developed as part of the SERA project, focusing on earthquake research infrastructure in Europe. The objectives included revisiting the 2013 model (ESHM13), updating input datasets and components, developing a new seismic hazard model with robust methods and uncertainty quantification, maintaining principles of consensus, transparency, and open access, updating seismogenic sources for the EC8 revision, revising the Ground Motion Prediction Equation logic tree based on new data, collaborating with relevant committees and experts, integrating ESHM20 into the Global Earthquake Mosaic, and enabling earthquake risk modelling in Europe at regional scale. This was extracted, adjusted in different locations and saved as a 10,000 year stochastic set.

A number of historical databases have been extracted giving previous intensities and event hazard metrics, and adapted for use as part of the MYRIAD-EU project as kriged raster and vector format files. In addition, a selection of 148 historic earthquakes, pre-1900, were remodelled based on available AHEAD intensity data. The selection of these 148 events was done to have a collection of up to 5 representative historic earthquake scenarios per European country. All are shown in Table 5 and examples in Appendix B: Figure 30.

Table 5: Overview of the produced, calibrated earthquake and triggered earthquake/aftershock hazard datasets to be used in the MYRIAD-EU project.

Peril	Type	Coverage	Name	Adaptation	Author
Earthquake	Stochastic	Europe	SERA-EU	Adjustment of a number of zones and application of the hazard model to produce a stochastic set of many possible earthquake footprints for each country (10,000 year stochastic set)	SERA Consortium and MYRIAD-EU
Earthquake	Stochastic	Eastern Europe	ECA	Stochastic set of intensity events through eastern Europe used in GFDRR Risk Profiles	Daniell and Schaefer 2014
Earthquake	Historic Set	Europe	AHEAD	All historic earthquake events from 1000 to 1903 in Europe as intensity points for each event	Extracted and remodelled from AHEAD
Earthquake	Historic Set	Europe	AHEAD	Shakemaps of the above intensities	MYRIAD-EU

Earthquake	Historic Set	Europe	USGS	Shakemaps from 1904 onwards	Extracted and remodelled from USGS
Earthquake	Historic Set	Europe	Risklayer	Additional Shakemaps where missing data and digitised big events from 1900 onwards	Daniell et al., 2018
Earthquake	Probabilistic	Europe	SERA-EU	Probabilistic map at various return periods (50, 100, 475, 975, 2475 years etc.)	SERA-EU, 2020
Earthquake	Probabilistic	Europe	SHARE	Probabilistic map at various return periods (50, 100, 475, 975, 2475 years etc.)	SHARE Consortium, 2013

Earthquakes on their own already show intrinsic characteristics of being a multi-hazard event, because especially large earthquakes do not only occur on their own, but with a sequence of aftershock events. Large aftershocks pose the potential to additionally damage or even destroy structures that have been already been pre-damaged by the initial mainshock, which is defined as the largest earthquake within the whole sequence. There are a variety of mathematical models to capture the nature of aftershock sequences (e.g. Utsu (1962), Zhuang (2012)) building on the well-established Omori-Utsu formula on temporal aftershock decay.

It is important to note that an aftershock model has also been adapted for use by Schaefer et al. (2017) and Schaefer et al. (2018), as part of the NARSIS project, and further adapted in MATRIX. The method allows us to characterise seismic sequences by their aftershock occurrence properties like decay rate and maximum expected aftershock magnitude. In combination with established intensity prediction equations and a general optimisation method to correlate historic aftershock sequence parameters to the concurrent events, a probabilistic impact map can be constructed.

This system can also be used to generate synthetic mainshock-aftershock sequences to assess the occurrence of ground motion over a longer period of time, including the temporal decay and probabilities of maximum magnitude aftershock events which are important multi-hazard events such as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Example aftershock impact map for the 2023 Turkey-Syria earthquake based on Schaefer et al. (2018).

3.3.2 Tsunami

Tsunamis pose a rare, but high-impact risk for many coasts of Europe. They usually originate from large earthquake-triggered seafloor displacements. However, they can also originate from volcanic eruptions as well as underwater and subaerial mass movements which enter larger water bodies. A challenging aspect in tsunami modelling is the extensive computation demand. Thus, probabilistic models with a very large number of individual events need to be simulated at a reduced resolution and inundation is assessed using empirical relationships between onshore sites and low resolution offshore points of interest. This approach is usually referred to as Peak Coastal Amplitude assessment. In addition, high resolution (<100 m) numerical inundation simulations are taken out on a scenario level.

Tsunami has two key models for Europe: 1) the model of Schäfer (2018); and (2) the model using the TSUMAPS NEAM project. The NEAM Tsunami Hazard Model 2018 (NEAMTHM18) is a probabilistic hazard model for tsunamis generated by earthquakes. It covers the coastlines of the North-East Atlantic, the Mediterranean, and connected Seas (NEAM). The hazard results are provided by hazard curves calculated at 2,343 Points of Interest (POI), distributed in the North-East Atlantic (1,076 POIs), the Mediterranean Sea (1,130 POIs), and the Black Sea (137 POIs) at an average spacing of ~20 km. For each POI, hazard curves are given for the mean, 2nd, 16th, 50th, 84th, and 98th percentiles.

Maps derived from hazard curves are probability maps for Maximum Inundation Heights (MIH) of 1, 2, 5, 10, 20 metres; and hazard maps for Average Return Periods (ARP) of 500, 1,000, 2,500, 5,000, 10,000 years. These can then be extrapolated to onshore locations. The TSUMAPS NEAM project modelled inundation height around Europe from 2016-2018 allowing for inundation heights (peak coastal amplitudes). This is shown in Figure 10. Similarly, the model of Schaefer et al. (2018) also computed peak coastal amplitudes, but at an average spacing of ~10 km along the coastlines, considering tsunami-genic earthquake sources offshore Crete, Cyprus, Sicily, Algeria as well as Portugal. Seismic sources around Crete and Portugal have historically been related to devastating tsunami events in the Eastern Mediterranean as well as the Atlantic coasts of Europe and Northern Africa. Both sources are thought to be capable of earthquakes of up to Mw=8.5 (Schaefer and Wenzel, 2019). An example is shown in Appendix B: Figure 31.

Both TSUMAPS-NEAM as well as Schaefer (2018) only cover earthquake-triggered tsunamis. Due to the complex nature of both volcanic and mass movement-triggered tsunamis and so far only obscure source characterisation, a probabilistic assessment of these hazards is not feasible at the current stage. However, certain representative or worst-case scenarios and historic reconstructions of specific events can be taken into account. The used sets are shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Overview of the produced, calibrated tsunami hazard datasets to be used in the MYRIAD-EU project.

Peril	Type	Coverage	Name	Adaptation	Author
Tsunami	Historic Set	Europe	Schaefer Catalogue	Remodelled Tsunamis from around Europe as part of a catalogue	Schaefer (2018)
Tsunami	Historic Set	Europe	NCEI Historical Runup	Runups from tsunamis from 2000BC onwards	NGDC (2023)
Tsunami	Probabilistic	Europe	TSUMAPS-NEAM	The most recent probabilistic tsunami catalogue in Europe, using a large stochastic event set built from historic tsunamis in order to create a detailed point based hazard curve catalogue.	Basili et al. 2019)

Figure 10: Probabilistic PCAs for tsunami hazards - TSUMAPS-NEAM providing hazard curves at every coastal point.

3.3.3 Wind

To capture wind hazards in Europe, the results of the PRIMAVERA project are utilised. The project aimed to produce advanced high-resolution global climate model datasets providing around 1300 years of windstorm data. These storm footprints were generated by identifying storms in the PRIMAVERA models through tracking. The resulting wind footprints underwent bias correction and were converted to 3s gusts on a uniform grid. The event set reduces uncertainty on return period magnitudes, reproduces the temporally clustered nature of European windstorms, and helps quantify the non-linear relationship between climate indices like the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) and windstorm damage. While the correlation between extended winter NAO and storm damage is moderate, the risk of extreme seasons varies significantly between negative and positive NAO states. However, caution is advised in interpreting damages for very long return periods due to the sensitivity of storm intensities to gust conversion and bias correction methods.

Those PRIMAVERA results provide 19 different simulation runs. Each run was resampled to provide a stochastic 10,000 year winter storm footprint database. In addition, for each simulation run, average expected return periods maps for 5, 10, 20, 50 and 100 years were compiled. Other datasets have also been downloaded for comparison and use within the project as seen in Table 7, with examples shown in Appendix B: Figure 32.

Table 7: Overview of the produced, calibrated wind hazard datasets to be used in the MYRIAD-EU.

Peril	Type	Coverage	Name	Adaptation	Author
Wind	Stochastic / Historic Set	Europe	PRIMAVERA	Stochastic set for Extratropical Storms in terms of wind speeds across Europe. This has been built using 20 realisations of around 65 years in order to create a 1000+ year stochastic set. These can be used as the historic wind tracks from 1950 to 2014; or as the stochastic set of different realisations	Lockwood et al. (2022)
Wind	Stochastic / Historic Set	Europe	WISC	Stochastic set of historic storms built for the insurance industry. It is	WISC (Koks et al. etc.)

				tailored to the large storm events in Europe.	
Wind	Probabilistic/ Historic Set	Europe	ERA-5	Reanalysis catalogue of wind speed events since 1940 including wind fields.	Extracted and applied to our regions
Wind	Historic Set	Europe	XWS	A historic wind field set over a number of different time steps from 1979 to 2012 with major storms in Europe.	
Wind	Probabilistic	Europe	RAIN	Probabilistic wind exceedance maps built from the model within the Delft led consortium RAIN including future scenarios	

3.3.4 Fluvial and Pluvial Flood

There exist numerous fluvial and pluvial flood models for Europe. A number of these studies are derived from global studies (i.e. Ward et al., 2020, GAR2015), a number are on a European scale (Alfieri et al., 2023), and some are at a regional scale (PIK: Hattermann et al. (2018)), and others are presented at country level or below i.e. the national flood maps of various countries to be used in MYRIAD-EU as shown in Table 8.

In addition, a number of historical footprints, and footprint databases have been sourced and adapted including Paprotny et al. (2020), the Global Flood Footprints Archive, Dartmouth Flood Observatory and some additional sources. For brevity, the entire flood map compendium table at the country scale and below has not been published here. This has been sourced specifically for the five case study regions and will be used in the final version of the deliverable. A few examples of the single event, probabilistic and stochastic sets are shown in Appendix B: Figure 33.

Table 8: Overview of the produced, calibrated flood datasets to be used in the MYRIAD-EU project.

Peril	Type	Coverage	Name	Adaptation	Author
Flood	Historic Set	Europe	Global Flood Footprints Archive	An effort by Cloud2Street and Google in order to derive flood footprints around the world. 934 flood footprints have been extracted from 2000 to 2018. A number of these are for Europe.	GEE
Flood	Historic Set	Europe	Derived HANZE	Using the HANZE database of Paprotny, we have applied the database and applied it spatially to NUTS3 data to derive the footprints	Paprotny et al., adapted.
Flood	Historic Set	Europe	DFO Footprints	Large database built since 1985 with major flood events globally and in Europe. The footprints are generally quite coarse.	Brakenridge et al.
Flood	Historic Set	Europe	ERA-5	Reanalysis catalogue of rainfall events, which are then rainfall derived footprints for input to rainfall-runoff models.	MYRIAD-EU
Flood	Probabilistic	Europe	JRC Flood Maps	Flood maps derived at multiple return periods for Europe	Dottori et al. 2016, Alfieri et al., 2018; with an update in 2023
Flood	Probabilistic	Europe		90m resolution flood map RFSM used at 1 return period	Bernhöfen et al. 2022

Flood	Probabilistic	Europe	GLOFRIS	90m resolution global flood maps	Downloadable through WRI; Ward et al., 2015
Flood	Probabilistic	Europe	National Flood Maps	Netherlands, Sweden, some states in Germany, TRI in France, Spain, Italy, Switzerland, Belgium, Eastern Europe.	Case study locations
Flood	Stochastic	Danube	PIK	Stochastic Event Set produced for the Danube with different return period historic maps	Hattermann et al., 2018

3.3.5 Landslide

Landslide hazards in Europe pose a significant threat to various regions, including the Alpine region, the Pyrenees, the Carpathians, and parts of the Mediterranean. The European Environment Agency (EEA) reports that landslide events in Europe have led to damage and loss values in the billions of euros, affecting roads, buildings, and agricultural land (EEA, 2020). Landslides can disrupt road and rail networks, causing closures and delays, damage power lines, gas pipelines, etc., affecting energy supply. Furthermore, landslides can have detrimental effects on agricultural areas and food production in mountainous regions, leading to soil erosion and loss of arable land. Addressing these landslide hazards in Europe requires comprehensive risk assessment and mitigation strategies to safeguard both human lives and the economies of affected regions.

In landslide risk assessment, historical landslide inventories are crucial, but global-scale assessments are hindered by incomplete inventories. In Europe, several essential databases and catalogues have been developed, each offering a unique perspective on this geological hazard. The Global Landslide Catalogue (GLC), maintained by NASA, stands as a global reference, documenting rainfall-triggered landslide events from 1970 to 2019. Its comprehensive coverage spans the globe, making it an invaluable resource for historical landslide analysis. On the European level, the European Landslide Susceptibility Map (ELSUS v2) created by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) provides high-resolution landslide susceptibility maps based on multivariate statistical methods, focusing on EU member states. The Pan-European Landslide Susceptibility Model (PELSM) from the European Geosciences Union (EGU) offers a broader pan-European evaluation of susceptibility, utilising advanced geostatistical methods. Meanwhile, the Eastern Europe Landslide Catalog delves into the unique context of Eastern Europe, reanalysing rainfall events to derive landslide footprints for rainfall-runoff models. Finally, the Central European Landslide Database provides detailed records of landslides in Central European countries, including valuable geological data. These resources collectively cover the landslide hazard at the European scale and can be drawn upon to implement a high-resolution landslide risk assessments.

Table 9: Overview of the produced, calibrated, downloaded landslide datasets to be used in the MYRIAD-EU project – examples are shown in Figure 34.

Type	Coverage	Name	Adaptation	Author
Historic Set	Europe	Global Landslide Catalog	The GLC considers all types of mass movements triggered by rainfall and impacts from 1970 to 2019. The Global Landslide Catalog (GLC) was developed with the goal of identifying rainfall-triggered landslide events around the world, regardless of size, impacts or location. The GLC considers all types of mass movements triggered by rainfall, which have been reported in the media, disaster databases, scientific reports, or other sources. The GLC has been compiled since 2007 at NASA Goddard Space Flight Center.	NASA
Probabilistic	Europe	ELSUS v2	High-resolution landslide susceptibility map covering EU member states based on statistical analysis.	JRC

Historic Set	Europe	PELSM	Pan-European Landslide Susceptibility Model - A model providing a pan-European evaluation of landslide susceptibility using advanced geostatistical methods.	EGU
Historic Set	Europe	Eastern Europe Landslide Catalog	Reanalysis catalogue of rainfall events, which are then rainfall derived footprints for input to rainfall-runoff models.	Eastern European Geosciences Association
Historic Set	Europe	Central European Landslide Database	Detailed records of landslides across Central European countries with geological data.	Central European Geological Survey

3.3.6 Tornado

Tornadoes are common throughout Europe, and have caused significant damage in most countries at different times in history. They bring significant damage ratios over the locations where they occur given the nature of tornado winds. In addition, they cut through transport, power, telecommunications and water networks, causing problems for networks in many cases.

The production of a stochastic hazard event set for Tornado was seen to be important given the probability of occurrence that it has over Europe. There are a number of different historic sets, and probabilistic hazard results that have been derived such as TorDACH, ESWD¹ and RAIN which give historic and probabilistic hazards (Appendix B: Figure 35).

The stochastic tornado set is built on occurrence probabilities of length, width and intensity on the Enhanced Fujita scale based on rates from historic European events. In addition, the wind direction and directionality of past tornadoes was taken into account as part of a stochastic process using Monte Carlo simulation and randomly selecting from the chosen data. Our stochastic tornado model shows 5000 years of potential tracks (F0-F5) for the Northern Adriatic in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Comparison of dataset outputs (single, probabilistic, stochastic) for tornado hazards. Upper: RAIN Project results, Middle: ESWD, Lower: Our Stochastic event set for Tornado.

¹ Unfortunately, due to restrictions, the ESWD database has not been sourced at this time but may be over the next months depending on choice of scenarios.

We have also collected a lot of different historical databases on top of these which are not necessarily geocoded.

Table 10: Overview of the produced, calibrated, downloaded tornado datasets to be used in the MYRIAD-EU project.

Peril	Type	Coverage	Name	Adaptation	Author
Tornado	Stochastic	Europe	MYRIAD-EU Tornado Set	22,000 year set of tornados on the basis of wind and historic frequency patterns	Risklayer
Tornado	Probabilistic	Europe	RAIN	A tornado occurrence probability map for current and future conditions as part of the RAIN FP7 project.	RAIN Consortium derived through ESWD

3.3.7 Hail

Hail damages are an important hazard for Europe (Punge et al., 2014) with many agricultural and equipment damages associated with this hazard. For particular industries and sectors, severe hailstorms have caused billions of Euros of damage (i.e. 1984 in Germany with the auto industry, 2013 in Germany for agriculture and buildings, 2014 in France and Belgium - particularly affecting wine and food production and 2022 again in France). In MYRIAD-EU, we see this hazard as being important for food and agriculture, as well as transport and infrastructure. In addition, this can affect tourism.

A couple of probabilistic models and maps have been collected, including some derived through Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (Appendix B: Figure 36), and through the RAIN project (as seen in Figure 12). ESWD and Keraunos data have not been collected due to the licensing nature of the databases.

Table 11: Overview of the produced, calibrated, downloaded hail datasets to be used in the MYRIAD-EU project.²

Peril	Type	Coverage	Name	Adaptation	Author
Hail	Probabilistic	Europe	EEA	High-resolution landslide susceptibility map covering EU member states based on statistical analysis.	KIT through EEA
Hail	Probabilistic	Europe	RAIN	A hail occurrence probability map of large and medium sized hail for current and future conditions as part of the RAIN FP7 project.	RAIN Consortium derived through ESWD

² Keraunos and ESWD data have not been sourced as part of the work. The ESWD data contains hail size etc.

Figure 12: Extreme hail probability per year over 5cm hail size derived from ESWD as part of the RAIN project.

3.3.8 Drought

Droughts, a pervasive environmental challenge, significantly impact regions such as Sub-Saharan Africa, the Middle East and North Africa, Australia, Southwest United States, Central Asia, India, and Europe. These areas, characterised by varying climatic and geographic features, frequently experience prolonged water scarcity. Influenced by factors like climate change, unsustainable agricultural practices, and water (mis)management, droughts in these regions are intensified by altered precipitation patterns, high temperatures, and overuse of water resources.

In Europe, the regions that are impacted by drought the most are located in the south and southeast, such as Spain, Italy, Greece, Portugal, and parts of Turkey and Bulgaria. The Mediterranean climate in these areas produces hot, dry summers and the increasing effects of climate change leads to reduced rainfall and higher temperatures. However, droughts are also now becoming a major theme in northern Europe. Historical drought data play a critical role in understanding patterns and impacts, aiding in the development of effective risk reduction strategies. Drought data have been captured by various datasets including OWDA, DFO, ERA-5, WRI and various historical datasets which allows for the use of reconstructions as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Examples for OWDA database extracted main drought events for 1540 and 2003 using June-July-August PSDI.

3.3.9 Wildfire

Annually, wildfires inflict significant damage on the environment, wildlife, human health and lives, and infrastructure across diverse regions, including Europe, Canada, the United States, the Amazon, the Arctic, Africa, Asia, and Australia. Wildfires are driven by key factors such as climate (change), unsustainable land use, deforestation, and natural or human ignition. Climate change intensifies wildfire risk through increased drought conditions, low relative humidity, dry lightning and strong winds. Unsustainable land use and environmental degradation diminish the resilience of natural ecosystems to wildfires, while deforestation and peatland drainage exacerbate drought conditions and elevate flammability (Koudenoukpo 2023).

In Europe, there is a general increasing trend in the number of wildfires and burnt areas since 2006, with recent critical years such as 2017 and 2021. In these critical years, the economic losses due to wildfires amounted to more than €2.5 billion. It is evident that there has been an increase in the extent of burnt areas in countries traditionally not prone to wildfires. Furthermore, the fire season has extended beyond the usual months of July, August, and September, with numerous wildfires and critical events occurring outside this period. Future climate projections show increasing fire danger levels in Europe. Increased fire danger levels will likely result in more intense fires and larger areas being burnt (European Commission 2023).

Historical wildfire data provide valuable insights into the occurrence, impact and intensity of past wildfires. For Europe, the EFFIS European Fire Database contains wildfire information compiled by EU Member States and other European countries. Since 2004, millions of wildfire records have been checked, stored and managed by JRC within EFFIS (Camia et al. 2014). Fire weather indices are commonly used to assess and understand meteorological fire hazards. They provide a measure of the daily fire danger (risk of fire occurrence, but also the expected rate of spread and fire intensity). There are a number of different fire weather indices that are based on simple algorithms that combine humidity and temperature information, while other more complex indices estimate both fire occurrence and severity (Steinfeld et al. 2022). The EFFIS fire danger forecast module offers access to fire danger indices based on numerical weather forecasts from two deterministic models, namely ECMWF (approximately 8 km) and MeteoFrance (approximately 10 km). The used sets are shown in Table 12.

Table 12: Overview of produced, calibrated, downloaded wildfire models and datasets.

Peril	Type	Coverage	Name	Adaptation	Author
Wildfire	Historic Set	Europe	EFFIS Burnt Area	Maps of burnt areas derived from the daily processing of MODIS satellite imagery at 250 m ground spatial resolution and Sentinel-2 imagery at 20 m spatial resolution	European Commission, JRC
Wildfire	Probabilistic	Europe	RAIN	Probabilistic datasets of high forest fire danger for the present climate (1981-2010) based on the ERA-Interim reanalysis and for the projected climates under the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios	Lehtonen et al. (2016)
Wildfire	Historic Reanalysis + Future	Europe	FWI		NEX-GDDP-CMIP6

3.3.10 Other Climatic, Hydrological and Geophysical Hazards

There are a number of other individual hazard datasets which can be used for combination, which have been downloaded.

1. Blizzard, Snow, Freezing Rain and Winter Weather (RAIN, ERA-5, KIT)
2. Thunderstorm and Lightning (RAIN, ERA-5)
3. Volcanic Hazards (GVM, Smithsonian, CATDAT)
4. Storm Surge / Wave Action / Coastal Impacts (Deltares, VUA, C3S Copernicus, GAR, CDRI)
5. ERA-5 Reanalysis concurrent hazards at an hourly basis – counts from 1940-2023.

These datasets have also been outputted and clipped for the various locations in Europe, however work is still ongoing towards the final deliverable. Given the number of hazards, not all will be fully detailed.

3.3.11 Ocean Metrics

The ocean, serving as the earth's primary carbon sink, has borne the brunt of anthropogenic global warming impacts by absorbing excess heat and energy released from rising greenhouse gas emissions trapped in the planet's system. This energy and heat absorption results in cascading effects such as ice-melting, sea-level rise, marine heatwaves, and ocean acidification, with profound and lasting consequences for marine biodiversity and the well-being of coastal communities and beyond (United Nations 2017).

As part of Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6), there are various models at European and global scale available to capture oceanic hazards. In addition, downscaled work capturing ocean metrics has been published in several other projects. Future scenarios of sea surface temperature, acidification, and sea level rise have been collected from C3S Copernicus along with some studies through the NEX-GDDP-CMIP6, and Climate Impact Lab (CIL) Global Downscaled Projections for Climate Impacts Research data.

The Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS) provides time series of global sea level related variables including tides, storm surges, and sea level rise from 1950 to 2050 derived from reanalysis and high resolution CMIP6 climate projections. The maps can be used for studies aiming to evaluate sea level variability, coastal flooding, coastal erosion, and accessibility of ports. In addition, GESLA Sea Level Rise data have been sourced. In addition, it provides daily estimates of global Sea Surface Temperature (SST) based on observations from multiple satellite sensors. SST is recognised as a crucial factor influencing global climate and weather patterns, playing pivotal roles in the exchange of energy, momentum, moisture, and gases between the ocean and atmosphere. Ocean acidification data have also been downloaded.

3.3.12 Biological Hazards

In terms of thinking of hazards which have multi-sector influence, the interaction of tiger mosquitoes in Europe is one which has significant implications for health, tourism, finance, and agriculture. Many such metrics are able to be extracted for existing work, however for the context of MYRIAD-EU, a focus on this one as a start has been made for use in the pilots. This uses the C3S Copernicus work and focusses on present-day hazard vs. 2050-2070 RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios looking at season length and suitability for mosquito breeding as seen in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Season length difference in days from 2050-2070 vs. 2000-2020 for tiger mosquitoes (top). Suitability on a scale (0 - 100) for tiger mosquitoes the periods of 2000-2020 (RCP4.5) and 2050-2070 (RCP8.5) (bottom).

Covid-19 statistics provide an important case study of hazard for multi-hazard interactions, where a change to the population, economy, health and other metrics occurs. Some 2.5 years of statistics and lockdown data exist spatially and temporally in order to allow for a delay in recovery, problems in social cohesion, health impacts has been collected including deaths, incidence and other metrics. Multiple datasets are present, including those produced by Risklayer since March 2020 (example for a significant day – 5th April 2021 - Figure 15), and those from WHO and JRC, which are ready for use within this project as needed and have been exchanged between consortium members already for use in different parts of the project.

Europe 7-day-incidence per subnational region

WHO European Region COVID-19 Explorer Data from JRC and national health agency COVID-19 portals

7-day-incidence (new Corona cases / 100,000 People / 7 days)

Map: Risklayer, CEDIM (KIT), @risklayer • Source: WHO-EURO, ECML JRC, EU Country European Datasets • Created with Datawrapper

Figure 15: Covid-19 statistics at a subnational level in terms of incidence per 100,000 population. Many other metrics such as deaths, hospitalisation, and other data were collected, in addition to data from JRC and European health ministry data.

3.4 The extension of the individual, triggered and consecutive hazard data above to multi-hazard frameworks

The extension and use of these individual/triggered secondary hazard data in multi-hazard analyses is done in a number of ways including using the time stamps associated with each historical set, allowing for correlations between events and locations to be made. The stochastic event sets also have a time stamp which allows for side-by-side temporal runs of overlapping hazards to find combinations of events exceeding certain thresholds. In addition, the duration time steps are being worked on currently to create the overlapping hazard time window; the overlapping impact window, and the operational impact window (i.e. time to recovery).

This duration choice will be explored further as part of the multi-hazard scenarios to be produced within the pilots. One such method that employs different durations of overlaps is the work of Claassen et al. (2023) as part of MYRIAD-HESA. The method is called MYRIAD-EU – Hazard Event Sets Algorithm (MYRIAD-HESA), and has been published as a scientific paper by Claassen et al. (2023). MYRIAD-HESA is a fully open-access method that can create multi-hazard event sets from any hazard events that occur on varying time, space, and intensity scales, by incorporating historic hazard footprint data. Hazard footprint data must include where the hazard occurred, as a spatial polygon, and when the hazard occurred, as a start and end date. Additionally, the hazard footprint can include the hazard intensity in some cases.

In MYRIAD-HESA, two or more hazards are considered a multi-hazard event if they overlap in both space and time, as seen in Figure 16. For example, Hazard 2 and Hazard 4 overlap in space, but not in time, and are therefore not considered a multi-hazard event. However, Hazard 3 does overlap in space and time with Hazard 4, these are multi-hazard events. Multi-hazard events can also consist of more than two hazards. This is the case with Hazard 1, Hazard 2, and Hazard 3, as there is a point in time where they all occur at the same location.

Figure 16: Example of a multi-hazard event set generation in MYRIAD-HESA without time-lag. This figure shows both hazard pairs and hazard groups. a) Hazards are a hazard group if all hazards overlap with each other in space and time as a pair. b) The dynamic hazards have to overlap with the other hazards during at least one of the overlapping time-steps.

A hazard can also be classified as a dynamic hazard. Dynamic hazards are those for which there is information on their spatial development through time. For example, a wildfire can spread or diminish over the span of its lifetime, leading to multiple event polygons for each individual

timestep. Therefore, if one or both hazards in a hazard pair are dynamic hazards, the dynamic polygons at each time step have to be checked to see whether the two hazards truly overlap at one point in space and time (as seen in Figure 16b). MYRIAD-HESA can also consider multi-hazard events where the second event occurs after the first one has ended by introducing a time-lag (see Figure 16a). Such a time-lag is the number of days after the first event during which a second event can occur. Hazards must overlap spatially to be considered a multi-hazard event, but no longer have to overlap directly in time. The algorithm enables a time-lag to be introduced for each hazard, where multiple hazards are considered a multi-hazard event if they occur within one another's time-lag. Various time-lags based on the hazard intensity have been tested to understand the impact of a time-lag on the number and type of multi-hazard events globally. The time-lag has also been applied to the dynamic hazards, as can be seen in Figure 16b.

Figure 17: a) The most frequent hazard pair in Europe per location. Here, there is no distinction which hazard occurs first in the pair, for example, 'dr & hw' could be a drought followed by a heat wave or a heat wave followed by a drought. White areas are the ocean or a place with no hazard

pairs. b) heatmap showing the number of hazard pairs in Europe. Hazard 1 is the hazard that started first, followed by Hazard 2, showing the number of pairs from 2004-2017.

On a European scale, different hazard pairs overlap between two hazards. The two most prominent hazard pairs in Figure 17a are the combination of droughts and heat waves as well as the combination of heat waves and extreme wind. The link between drought and heat waves is evident, as high temperatures can lead to dry conditions and dry conditions can further increase temperatures. Moreover, the combination of a drought and a heat wave is a typical compound event that has received much attention in the past years as they usually lead to severe impacts on socioeconomic factors, are widespread, and are likely to intensify under climate change (Sutanto et al., 2020; Zscheischler et al., 2018). In contrast, the link between heat waves and extreme wind is less evident in literature. In this study, heat waves are based on above average temperatures of specific calendar days. This means, for example, that heat waves during the European winter storm season, may not necessarily be a typical ‘hot’ summer day. An extreme example of such a winter heat wave is the unprecedented temperatures Europe experienced in January 2023, where temperatures were 10°C above average and records were broken by 4°C. The overlap between extreme wind and heat waves in Europe is predominantly a result of such warm winter weather. Additionally, we observe many pairs that include a flood, such as in the UK where the combination between floods and extreme wind are the most frequent hazard pair. Here, the extreme wind event is likely a storm that is paired with storm surge and/or (extreme) precipitation, commonly referred to as a compound flood. Finally, there appear to be many hazard pairs that consist of heat waves and wildfires. This hazard pair is less visible in Figure 17a as there are many small events as seen in Figure 17b.

In summary, MYRIAD-HESA showcases that Europe and the world are at risk to a large range of different multi-hazards. To further study these multi-hazards events, MYRIAD-HESA will be available on the MYRIAD-EU Zenodo community, providing flexibility to conduct multi-risk assessments by, for example, incorporating higher resolution data for an area of interest. Alongside MYRIAD-HESA, the multi-hazard event sets, MYRIAD-HESA, will also be openly available to further increase the understanding of multi-hazard events in the disaster risk community.

Leading into the software

These hazards can be placed on top of one another, in order to give the respective values of each dataset at a certain point, and the different agencies that are available for datasets where values are not directly available, however this is ongoing work and will be produced as part of the software. The coding for the implementation of location based metrics has been implemented already as part of the pre-coding as seen below, which allows for temporal overlap views and readouts of the values at a particular site in Europe for multiple hazards (Figure 18).

Figure 18: Code-implemented data outputs across Europe as part of the initial stage software development for multiple hazard results of historical and probabilistic results. Stochastic sets are implemented differently.

The software is not part of the interim deliverable, however, the extraction from the hazard and exposure sets has been tested to allow for the outputting of values at any location in Europe. This will be extended to include the durations associated with the events and a threshold choice analyst module.

3.5 Vulnerability data and fragility data of use for direct and indirect multi-hazard and multi-risk scenarios

This section will be developed by Risklayer for the final deliverable, however many vulnerability functions have already been sourced and been put into the mock software interface (Figure 19).

Figure 19: Initial software implementation.

It will include:

1. A review of vulnerability functions for single overlapping hazards and multiple surface style functions using Gehl et al., existing software solutions, NARSIS thresholds etc.
2. A review of the vulnerability data collected per sector for European use.
3. The formatting of the vulnerability data for intercompatible use in MYRIAD-EU
4. The vulnerability data tool for inputting the correct format for vulnerability and visualising existing functions from the aforementioned review.

4 Case Study Specific Multi-risk Scenario Modelling

4.1 What is needed for the MYRIAD-EU pilots to model their sectoral risks?

MYRIAD-EU requires a series of risk outputs for each pilot location and sector. The hazard, exposure, vulnerability and datasets above in Chapter 3 give the baseline and the datasets needed to calculate risk. However, this does not define the specific loss or risk metrics to be calculated in each pilot location. To address this, we propose a criteria-based approach for selecting loss and risk metrics, focusing on their relevance to the specific environmental and socio-economic contexts of each pilot location. Metrics should be aligned with the primary risk factors identified in these regions, ensuring that they accurately reflect the unique challenges and vulnerabilities that each area faces.

Thus, a logical starting point is a theoretical analysis of different loss and damage parameters that are produced in sectoral risk assessments in order to determine what the best potential parameters are. This analysis will evaluate the suitability of various parameters, considering factors such as data availability, reliability, and relevance to sector-specific risks. The outcome will guide the selection of parameters that offer the most significant insights for risk mitigation and policy.

The following inform the evaluation:

- Hazard, Exposure and Vulnerability Sets derived for the Pilots both for current and future conditions
- What is possible from a WP5-4 perspective looking at the overall work plan (D3.2b) in in the pilots and the dynamic changes in vulnerability if modelling over time or in the future; or within an event sequence
- Understanding the requirements of pilots via the Interim report on implementation and testing of MYRIAD-EU methods and tools in each Pilot (D3.3a)
- What datasets are available in addition to the above points?

In a first example for the Canary Islands, the following potential risk metrics were identified as a starting point:

Infrastructure & Transport Sector

- Lost accessibility to health services (Social Metric)
- Supply-chain disruptions (Economic Metric)
- Road closures (Economic Metric)
- Fatal Accident Rate (expected number of fatalities per unit of exposure) (Social Metric)
- Potential Loss of Life (expected number of fatalities within a specified population during a specified period of time) (Social Metric)

Food & Agriculture Sector

- Depending on seasonal occurrence → loss of revenues (because of disrupted transport infrastructure) (Economic Metric)
- Fertility loss of soil due to salinisation (Economic Metric)
- Lost no. of fish or tonnage of fish lost (Economic Metric)
- No. of lost boats (Social & Economic Metric)
- Loss of number of fishing ships (Economic Metric)
- Contamination of drinkable water (Environmental Metric)

Ecosystems & Forestry Sector

- Leaf area index (LAI) reduction (Environmental Metric)
- impacts on biodiversity (Environmental Metric)

- % damage to forest from salt water intrusion (Environmental Metric)
- No. of lost species (Environmental Metric)

Energy Sector

- Access to electricity at the household level (Social Metric)
- Business disruption due to power failures (Economic Metric)
- Resilience of the power network (Social Metric)
- Refined petroleum export (Economic Metric)

Finance Sector

- Increased risk to real-estate market (Economic Metric)
- Decreased return on capital assets (Economic Metric)
- Number of insurance claims (Economic Metric)
- Pure damage metrics (Economic Metric)

Tourism Sector

- Reduction in the number of tourists (Social Metric)
- No. of affected hotels (Economic Metric)
- Number of tourism sites affected / closed (Economic Metric)
- Job loss (Economic Metric)

Other metrics could include the following:

- Transportation (e.g., measured as length in kilometres of damaged/destroyed roads and railways; number of damaged/destroyed bridges, airports, marine ports)
- Water and Sanitation (e.g., measured as length in kilometres of damaged/destroyed water infrastructure; number of damaged/destroyed water and waste treatment facilities)
- Energy (e.g., measured as length in kilometres of damaged/destroyed power grids, number of damaged/destroyed power plants, number of offshore energy platforms, miles of pipeline)
- Communication (e.g., measured as length in kilometres of damaged/destroyed telephone communication or broadband cables, number of cell phone towers damaged/destroyed)
- Education (e.g., measured as number of schools damaged/destroyed)
- Health infrastructure (e.g., measured as number of hospitals damaged/destroyed)
- Government and Public Buildings (e.g. measured as number of buildings damaged/destroyed)
- Agriculture and Forestry (e.g., measured as number of livestock lost, tonnes/acreage of crops damaged/destroyed, timber loss, crop insurance payments)

It is important as well to classify what parts would be covered under quantitative, semi-quantitative, and qualitative methods. We will take into account the specific characteristics of these datasets, including their spatial and temporal resolution, coverage, and compatibility with modelling frameworks. This will ensure that the chosen method aligns with the data characteristics and the objectives of the risk assessment.

Table 13: Definition of direct and indirect losses as well as tangible and intangible ones.

	Tangible	Intangible	Market Value
Direct losses	Material (in the sense that they can be touched) losses due to the direct contact with the respective hazard. Example: Houses, Infrastructure, Forest, Lives	Immaterial effects Example: Loss of life	Direct losses (tangible or intangible) that have a market value or can be reasonably measured in monetary terms or non-market impacts.
Indirect losses	Occur as a result of the direct impacts. Example: supply chain interruption	Occur as a result of the direct impacts Example: impacts on mental health	Indirect losses (tangible or intangible) that have a market value or can be reasonably measured in monetary terms or non-market impacts.

There are often basic sets of key loss metrics that are generally capital based when looking at financial impacts such as in Table 13. These are often the easiest to quantify. We will quantify these metrics, considering both traditional approaches and innovative techniques that leverage new data sources and technologies.

The Interim report on implementation and testing of MYRIAD-EU methods and tools in each Pilot (D3.3a) gave insights into the challenges in multi-hazard risk assessment, including the significance of comprehensive data collection, stakeholder engagement, and interdisciplinary collaboration. These insights have informed our approach towards developing advanced methods for generating hazard event sets and quantifying risk, ensuring that the scenarios we develop are scientifically robust and practically relevant to the pilot locations, including the target sectors and stakeholders, and compatible with the data that the pilots are collecting or intending to collect. The report highlighted the need to select appropriate combinations of methods for multi-risk assessment and management that respond to specific challenges by creating clear risk metrics such as in Table 14. Challenges were also identified in developing multi hazard and risk scenarios, such as inadequate governance, lack of data, and the complexity of translating scientific findings into policy and practice. The report supported the notion that developing hazard event sets and calculating risk is an iterative process that benefits from the collaborative input of various stakeholders and experts. The report identified certain challenges and opportunities, like governance issues and knowledge gaps that are common across different regions and scenarios. Finally, the report highlighted the need for applying advanced modelling tools and techniques for effective risk assessment and management.

Table 14: Overview of information schemes and respective data variables. These define the risk metrics to be calculated which define the modelling approach.

Information Theme	Variables in Database
Socio-economic Event Indicators	Population, socio-economic data, indicators relating to wealth, social status, health etc., exchange rates,
Social Loss Parameters	Deaths, Injuries, Homelessness, Affected
Infrastructure and other Loss Parameters	Building damage classes, Infrastructure damage classes, Other non-structural damage
Secondary Effect Parameters	Socioeconomic losses due to secondary effects such as for earthquake: tsunami, liquefaction, landslide, fault rupture, fire, NaTech (Natural Disasters causing Technological Disasters etc.); for volcano – not only tephra etc.
Economic Loss Parameters	Direct, Indirect, Aid, Sectoral, Capital Stock vs. Production losses
Economic Cost parameters	Reconstruction as well as replacement cost methods not taking into account building exposure.
Exposure Information	No. of buildings, typologies, code use, vulnerability details

4.2 Development of Direct Hazard and Risk Methods and Datasets for the pilots

This section gives the background methodologies for the hazard and risk scenarios in order to give a more in-depth view of how certain hazards and risk metrics can be calculated spatially and temporally. It first details how the direct quantitative risk metrics are derived using hazard, exposure and vulnerability functions for the different hazards and exposure metrics for the sectors within MYRIAD-EU. In a second instance, fragility functions are shown explaining damage class methods to be used. This gives a clear framework for the understanding of the pilots for vulnerability and fragility functions. The qualitative and indirect risk methodologies are also then described.

The methodologies are applicable for the current and future conditions at static points in time. It is important to look at spatial and temporal dynamics if the risk elements have a large spatial distribution, as there will not be the same static change in hazard or exposure over time at two different locations.

4.2.1 Direct Risk Function Basis for event scenario analysis

4.2.1.1 Hazard Component (H)

The hazard component (H) is the first component required as part of an event scenario analysis. For the different MYRIAD-EU hazards to be examined, these have the following format but can differ depending on the location, style and analysis element required. For instance, for bridges and earthquake shaking, damage correlates best with Sd (spectral displacement) instead of Sa (spectral acceleration) which is commonly used for buildings. This is to do with the structural dynamics of the bridge with respect to the earthquake shaking.

For each type of natural peril, define the hazard metric (H) as follows with some example metrics:

- Earthquake: $H_{eq} = Sa$ or MMI or some other such parameter depending on E (exposure type)
- Volcanic Tephra: $H_{vol} = kPa$
- Flood: $H_{fl} = \text{Depth in metres}$
- Wind: $H_{wind} = \text{Velocity in m/s}$
- Tornado: $H_{tor} = F_{scale}$ or Velocity in m/s
- Landslide: $H_{ls} = \text{Volume in } m^3$
- Hail: $H_{hail} = KE$ or $\text{Maximum Size in mm}$
- Drought: $H_{drought} = \text{Water Reduction in } m^3/s$ or $\text{Yield Reduction in tonnes}$
- Wildfire: $H_{fire} = \text{Intensity in kW/m}$
- Winter Weather: $H_{winter} = \text{Snow Depth in cm}$ or $\text{Temperature in degrees}$
- Ocean Acidification: $H_{oa} = pH$
- Tsunami: $H_{tsu} = \text{Wave Height in m}$ or $\text{Wave Velocity in m/s}$
- Lightning: $H_{light} = \text{Voltage in kV}$

4.2.1.2 Exposure Component (E)

The exposure component quantifies the elements at risk in the event of a natural hazard. This can be measured in various units, depending on the element and sector in question:

a. *Infrastructure and Transport Sector (E_infra)*

- Value: Monetary value or replacement cost of buildings, roads, bridges, etc.
- Elements: Number of buildings, length of roads, number of bridges, etc.
- Capacity: Daily traffic volume, transportation capacity, etc.
- People: Population using the infrastructure daily.

b. *Food and Agriculture Sector (E_agri)*

- Value: Market value of crops, livestock, and other agricultural assets.
- Elements: Number of farms, quantity of crops, headcount of livestock, etc.
- Area: Land area under cultivation, size of pastures, etc.
- Production: Volume of agricultural produce, productivity metrics.

c. *Ecosystems and Forestry Sector (E_eco)*

- Value: Economic valuation of ecosystem services.
- Elements: Number of species, conservation status.
- Area: Square kilometres of natural reserves, forests.
- Biodiversity: Biodiversity indices, habitat quality metrics.

d. *Energy Sector (E_energy)*

- Value: Valuation of energy-producing assets and reserves.
- Elements: Number and capacity of power plants, length of power lines.
- Capacity: Energy production and distribution capacity.
- People: Number of consumers served by the energy infrastructure.

e. *Finance (including buildings) Sector (E_finance)*

- Value: Economic value of financial assets, insured values of properties.
- Elements: Number of financial institutions, quantity of insured buildings.
- Transactions: Volume and value of financial transactions.
- People: Employees in the sector, number of customers.

f. *Tourism Sector (E_tourism)*

- Value: Revenue from tourism-related activities, replacement cost of hotels etc.
- Elements: Number of hotels, tourist attractions.
- Capacity: Visitor capacity, accommodation capacity.
- People: Number of tourists, employment in tourism.

For each sector, the exposure at a location can be expressed as a vector of these elements:

$E_{location} = [Value, Elements, Capacity, People]$ or a single one of these.

Section 3.2 provides the tools for exposure at risk calculations in overlapping scenarios for many different hazards (Section 3.3) even without moving to a full risk calculation.

These exposure at risk calculations can provide a useful metric to be used in DAPP or in any discussions within sectors before an entire risk analysis. Thus, even stopping the direct risk calculation at this point can give a useful metric in the absence of vulnerability, when looking at overlapping hazard types.

4.2.1.3 Vulnerability Component with Location (V)

The vulnerability functions relate the hazard metric to the expected damageability of the exposed element at specific locations:

$$V_{location}(H) = a_{location} \cdot H^{b_{location}}$$

$$DR_{location} = V_{location}(H) \cdot E_{location}$$

$$D_{location} = DR_{location} \cdot E_{location}$$

These are mainly pre-compiled for the different software and methods used in MYRIAD-EU and incorporate a beta distribution. For each cell in the Damage Assessment Matrix, estimate the damage ratio as a random variable that follows a beta distribution.

The parameters alpha and beta are shaped based on historical data and expert judgment about the expected range and most likely values of the damage ratios. The beta distribution is bounded between 0 and 1, making it appropriate for modelling ratios.

The beta distribution is employed in risk modelling to represent the uncertainty in the damage assessments due to variability in both the natural hazards and the vulnerability of the exposed elements. When combined with the Damage Assessment Matrix, the beta distribution provides a probabilistic framework for each entry in the matrix, reflecting the confidence intervals around the expected damages.

4.2.1.4 Outputting D_matrix (Damage Assessment Matrix)

To output a Damage Assessment Matrix (D_matrix) – essentially a damage ratio at each location that only considers "Elements" from the Exposure component for six different sectors, we follow these steps – now this would be simplified for any location for a singular exposure at a time, but we will keep all examples here for the benefit of the sectors and pilots so they can see their approach brought forward:

a. Step 1: Define Exposure for Each Sector

For each sector, define the exposure in terms of the number of elements (e.g., buildings, roads, farms) at risk:

- E_{infra} : Number of infrastructure elements (e.g., buildings, bridges).
- E_{agri} : Number of agricultural elements (e.g., farms, livestock units).
- E_{eco} : Number of ecosystem elements (e.g., protected areas, key species habitats).
- E_{energy} : Number of energy elements (e.g., power plants, substations).
- $E_{finance}$: Number of financial elements (e.g., banks, insured properties).
- $E_{tourism}$: Number of tourism elements (e.g., hotels, tourist attractions).

b. Step 2: Define Vulnerability for Each Sector

For each sector, define a vulnerability function that relates the hazard metric to the expected damageability of the elements:

- $V_{infra}(H)$
- $V_{agri}(H)$
- $V_{eco}(H)$
- $V_{energy}(H)$
- $V_{finance}(H)$

- $V_{tourism}(H)$

These functions are sector-specific and derived from historical data, expert judgment, or empirical studies. These are the style of functions as seen in the vulnerability interface in Section 3.5.

c. Step 3: Calculate Damage Ratios

For each element within each sector, calculate a damage ratio using the appropriate vulnerability function:

$$\begin{aligned}
 DR_{infra} &= V_{infra}(H) \times E_{infra} \\
 DR_{agri} &= V_{agri}(H) \times E_{agri} \\
 DR_{eco} &= V_{eco}(H) \times E_{eco} \\
 DR_{energy} &= V_{energy}(H) \times E_{energy} \\
 DR_{finance} &= V_{finance}(H) \times E_{finance} \\
 DR_{tourism} &= V_{tourism}(H) \times E_{tourism}
 \end{aligned}$$

d. Step 4: Construct the Damage Assessment Matrix (D_{matrix})

Create a matrix where each row represents a location and each column represents a sector. Each cell in the matrix contains the expected damage for that sector at that location, based on the damage ratios:

$$D_{matrix} = \begin{bmatrix} DR_{infra, Location1} & DR_{agri, Location1} & \dots & DR_{tourism, Location1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ DR_{infra, LocationN} & DR_{agri, LocationN} & \dots & DR_{tourism, LocationN} \end{bmatrix}$$

e. Step 5: Output the D_{matrix}

Present the Damage Assessment Matrix as the output, where each entry $D_{i,j}$ represents the expected damage for sector j at location i , based solely on the "Elements" of exposure.

These can be then summed to produce the final damage result, or aggregated at various levels of resolution over the locations.

4.2.1.5 Outputting D_{matrix} (Damage Assessment Matrix) at multiple events and for multiple exposure components.

We are now moving to multiple events and exposure components. The same Damage Assessment Matrix quantifies the expected damages across different sectors and locations. It is constructed using the damage ratios calculated from the vulnerability functions and the exposure elements.

$$E_{matrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Value_1 & Elements_1 & Capacity_1 & People_1 \\ Value_2 & Elements_2 & Capacity_2 & People_2 \\ Value_3 & Elements_3 & Capacity_3 & People_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$HV_{matrix} = \begin{bmatrix} V_{H1,Location1} & V_{H2,Location1} \\ V_{H1,Location2} & V_{H2,Location2} \\ V_{H1,Location3} & V_{H2,Location3} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$D_{\text{matrix}} = \begin{bmatrix} DR_{\text{infra, Location1}} & DR_{\text{agri, Location1}} & \dots & DR_{\text{tourism, Location1}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ DR_{\text{infra, LocationN}} & DR_{\text{agri, LocationN}} & \dots & DR_{\text{tourism, LocationN}} \end{bmatrix}$$

That provides the simple damage calculation, however the temporal aspect of damages and the hazards themselves also can be taken into account to calculate the damage from two concurrent events of different types, or the same type.

$$D_{\text{concurrent}} = f(D_{\text{type1}}, D_{\text{type2}}, \dots)$$

However, two parts are important: the duration of hazards (as seen in Figure 20 for the different hazard types), and the duration of the damage and repair (the operational time window as coined in NARSIS) and the dynamic nature of the exposure and vulnerability themselves. These can be kept static or be employed. First to hazard:

When looking at two different hazard types: t_{h1}, t_{h2} : Duration of hazard types 1 and 2. In the following diagram N1-N73 are from the ASAMPSA-E project which defined numerous natural hazard classes (Figure 20). Depending on magnitude and sequencing, the different hazard types have a dominant hazard in terms of temporal overlap and a hazard of shorter duration.

Figure 20: Mean pairing duration (seconds), the X and Y labels indicate the cross-correlation of the hazards which are detailed in the Annex B spreadsheets from N1-N73 in line with an adjustment of the ASAMPSA_E definitions.

To account for the complexity of real-world scenarios, we need to integrate the formula over the duration of the hazards and consider the rate of change of vulnerability and exposure over time. This overlaps with D4.3 and would be the way that the dynamic vulnerability functions come into

the analysis. This might require a more dynamic model, potentially involving differential equations to simulate the time-varying nature of the hazards and their impacts.

Let's denote:

- t_{h1}, t_{h2} : Duration of hazard types 1 and 2.
- t_{d1}, t_{d2} : Duration of damage effects from hazard types 1 and 2.
- $E(t)$: Time-varying exposure.
- $V_1(t), V_2(t)$: Time-varying vulnerability functions for hazard types 1 and 2.
- $H_1(t), H_2(t)$: Time-varying hazard intensities for hazard types 1 and 2.
- $I_{combined}(t)$: Time-varying combined impact at a location.

The combined impact $I_{combined}(t)$, considering the overlapping and sequential nature of hazards, is formulated as:

$$I_{combined}(t) = \int_0^{t_{end}} (V_1(t) \cdot E(t) \cdot H_1(t) + V_2(t) \cdot E(t) \cdot H_2(t) - \text{OverlapAdjustment}(t)) dt$$

The function $\text{OverlapAdjustment}(t)$ accounts for the overlapping duration of hazards and their damage effects. The actual form of this function will depend on the specific interaction between the two hazards.

The overlap adjustment function could be expressed, for example, as:

$$\text{OverlapAdjustment}(t) = \min(V_1(t) \cdot H_1(t), V_2(t) \cdot H_2(t)) \cdot E(t) \cdot O(t)$$

where $O(t)$ is a function that quantifies the extent of overlap based on the timing and duration of the hazards.

This integral represents the cumulative effect of both hazards over time, with adjustments for how exposure and vulnerability change during this period. Solving this integral requires specific functional forms for $V_1(t)$, $V_2(t)$, $E(t)$, $H_1(t)$, and $H_2(t)$, along with empirical data for validation.

There are even greater complexities when the hazards are dependent on one another with the introduction of different correlations between hazard probabilities and onset times. Given the practical complexities of modelling such interactions, the independent scenarios of a multi-hazard and multi-risk nature will be first focused on in order to cover practical solutions for the pilots and sectors.

4.2.1.6 Stochastic Event Sets and Concurrent Hazards

For a comprehensive risk assessment, we consider a hypothetical 10,000-year stochastic event set in most cases and the occurrence of concurrent hazards at the same location. Within each of these years, 0, 1 or more than 1 event can occur, then temporal analysis is required.

Assigning a year and time to each event allows for the analysis of hazard occurrences and the identification of overlapping events throughout the time span.

At case study scale, the European datasets and methods can be used plus additional smaller scale models if/as available however it depends on the chosen metrics.

These can be undertaken using future scenarios over a time period using the influence of RCP-SSP scenarios or for a current time step basis. More will be discussed in the final version of the deliverable once finalised.

4.2.2 Direct Fragility Function Basis for event risk scenario analysis

Fragility functions assign probabilities to different damage levels based on hazard intensity, exposure type, and element vulnerability. Typically, damage is defined in the pure insurance sense of a damage ratio of a single building or a group of buildings.

$$DR = \frac{\text{Repair Cost}}{\text{Replacement Cost}} \text{ for a single building}$$

$$MDR = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(\text{Repair Cost})_i}{(\text{Replacement Cost})_i} \text{ for a group of buildings}$$

In vulnerability functions, existing economic loss models are usually created as a direct calculation of property values multiplied by some form of direct vulnerability-hazard function as shown in the above section, to give the direct economic damage result. However, moving to fragility functions, for buildings, the floor area is usually given a certain value, which is multiplied by the total built-up area in the same way as is the case in usual exposure modelling, but then assigned a certain damage grade in order to create a loss estimate. The following equation is defined through the same form used in SEISVARA (Haldar et al. (2013)) for the cost of building damage in an occupancy class of different building types (but is essentially repeated in all software packages examining direct economic damages):

$$Cost_{Occ} = \sum_{Build=1}^N \left[FA_{Build,Occ} \times TFA_{Occ} \times \sum_{DS=1}^5 (P(Gr_{DS})_{build} \times LR_{DS}) \times RCost_{build} \right]$$

where the following are defined:

$FA_{Build,Occ}$ = the floor area for a particular model building type (MBT) in a particular occupancy class I, as a percentage of the total floor area

TFA_{Occ} = the total floor area in an occupancy class (i.e. residential)

$P(Gr_{DS})_{build}$ = the probability of the damage state (DS=1-5) occurring for a particular building type

LR_{DS} = the loss ratio for a particular damage state (i.e. DS=1 is 3%, DS=2 is 7% etc.)

$RCost_{build}$ = the replacement cost for a building – generally defined through material costs, labour etc.

Much the same can be done for fatalities, by assigning the rate of deaths per damage class; or for homelessness. See SYNER-G: Daniell et al. (2014) on the production of fatality functions for building superclasses, or Khazai et al. (2014) for the shelter/homelessness from building damage for earthquakes. Similar functions have been derived for other hazards.

But what does this look like in a practical sense for other generic exposure elements?:

$P_{di}(H)$: Probability of damage class i occurring, given a hazard intensity H .

C_i : Damage class i , ranging from 0 (no damage) to n (complete damage).

L_i : Loss ratio for damage class i , indicating the proportion of value lost.

t_{ri} : Duration of repair correlated to damage class i .

E : Exposure, which could be the value or number of elements at risk.

V : Vulnerability of the elements at risk.

H : Hazard intensity.

D_{total} : Total expected damage.

The total expected damage can be modelled as:

$$D_{total} = \sum_{i=0}^n P_{di}(H) \cdot L_i \cdot E$$

where $P_{di}(H)$ is determined by the fragility function for each damage class.

The duration of repair t_{r_i} is associated with the damage class and can be represented as:

$$t_{r_i} = \text{function of } C_i \text{ (possibly a lookup table or empirical formula)}$$

The loss ratio L_i for each damage class is defined as:

$$L_i = \text{percentage loss for class } C_i$$

To calculate the combined impact with consideration for repair duration, the formula extends to integrate the loss over the repair time for each damage class:

$$I_{combined} = \sum_{i=0}^n \left(\int_0^{t_{r_i}} P_{di}(H) \cdot L_i \cdot E \cdot V \cdot dt \right)$$

This integral sums the losses over time until repair, weighted by the probability of each damage class given the hazard intensity. It integrates this over the set of damage outcomes provided by the fragility functions. $P_{di}(H)$ is determined by evaluating the fragility curves at a given hazard intensity H . These curves are empirically constructed or obtained through simulations through Section 3.5, providing the probability of each damage class at different levels of hazard intensity. The vulnerability V may adjust these probabilities based on the characteristics of the exposed elements.

Fragility functions for infrastructure, such as bridges during earthquakes, typically categorise damage into discrete classes with associated probabilities based on the seismic intensity measure. These classes are linked to varying durations of repair and recovery.

For instance, bridge damage classes and their associated repair times might be:

No Damage: 0 days repair time.

Slight Damage: Up to 1 week repair time.

Moderate Damage: 1 to 6 months repair time.

Extensive Damage: 6 to 24 months repair time.

Complete Damage: More than 24 months repair time.

The probabilities of each damage class occurring are determined by the fragility curves, which are functions of seismic intensity measures like peak ground displacement.

The expected damage and associated repair times can again be integrated over the duration of the hazard to calculate the total impact as per the formula given above for $I_{combined}$:

$$D_{total} = \sum_{i=0}^n \int_0^{t_{r_i}} P_{di}(H) \cdot L_i \cdot E \cdot V \cdot dt$$

where $P_{di}(H)$ is the probability of damage class i , L_i is the loss ratio for damage class i , and t_{r_i} is the duration of repair for damage class i .

4.2.3 Direct Qualitative Risk Basis for event scenario analysis

To complement quantitative modelling approaches outlined in 4.2.1 and 4.2.2 and better address risk scenarios from a holistic sense, qualitative methods can be used. In this context, indicator-based approaches are a key component of integrated risk assessments to develop measures and pathways for reducing risk and as a means to measure, monitor and evaluate overall risk over time. Various indicator frameworks have been developed by local governments, multilateral institutions and academics around the world to measure resilience of communities and cities, including for the infrastructure and different sectors encompassed in urban agglomerations.

Indicator approaches vary in their theoretical underpinnings, indicator selection, weighting, and aggregation methods. They typically utilise either publicly available data and employ multi-criteria assessment to create composite indices or rely on predetermined sets of qualitative indicators to compare spatial regions uniformly. Indicator-based frameworks based on publicly available secondary data often generally neglect the need to dynamically adjust indicators to the context of specific places, people, and organisations. To capture local processes for decision-making and the production of relevant indicators and targets for producing actionable information, different types of indicators that are representative of the local knowledge, conditions, and context are needed. These types of indicators require the design of targeted surveys and a participatory approach in the design of the indicators with the intended target beneficiaries.

Using the tourism lens, a qualitative methodology and approach is being developed founded on the recognition that resilience in a tourism destination entails understanding the feedback mechanism and systemic risks across multiple interdependent sectors such as infrastructure and transportation, energy, finance, agriculture and food within a destination.

We have introduced a Scorecard methodology aimed at evaluating destinations based on Critical Success Factors (CSF) associated with multi-risk and multi-sector destination resilience aligning directly with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (SFDRR). The Destination Resilience Scorecard incorporates qualitative input from key stakeholders and globally recognised best practices, as well as quantitative metrics derived from climate and catastrophe risk modelling, environmental indicators, and tourism-related metrics.

The qualitative Scorecard combines quantitative and qualitative destination CSFs, contextualising criteria across multiple sectors in a destination to match local destination attributes and strategic actions through a participatory process involving stakeholders. This approach ensures the practical applicability of the framework and seeks to create a sense of ownership among the pilot stakeholders where the methodology is applied with regard to destination resilience efforts.

We adhere to a four-phased approach as shown in Figure 21 that underscores the delivery of recommendations underpinned by measurable metrics. The metrics or assessment criteria of the Scorecard will be informed by the “Storyline” approach used in the Canary Island pilot which provides the systems definition and context around dimensions of resilience to be measured. In this pilot, the connection between the Scorecard approach and the DAPP methodology will also be explored. One potential application will be to use the Scorecard as an overall monitoring and evaluation tool for measuring progress on resilience performance within the destination by integrating the results of the DAPP.

Figure 21: Schematic for the application in the pilot projects.

The following are examples of qualitative criteria that can be developed along several CSFs as dimensions for assessing risk and resilience in a destination. Each of the first four CSFs are anchored into the four priorities of action and targets of the 2015-2030 Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction. These will have to be contextualized in the pilot application to the systems definition and key issues and priorities emerging in the pilot, while at the same time ensuring the link to the four Sendai priorities as part of the methodology. Accordingly, the Scorecard will evaluate and rate the resilience performance over time of a tourism destination across multiple sectors based on these contextualized CSFs:

CSF 1: Understanding Multi-Sectoral Risks to Tourism

Questions under this CSF can assess the destination's level of awareness and understanding of various risks to tourism. Scores can be assigned based on the depth of knowledge regarding disaster risks, climate change impacts, and other potential disruptions to the tourism sector.

CSF 2: Managing Destination Resilience

This CSF evaluates the destination's preparedness and management of resilience. Scores can be assigned based on the existence of budget allocations, formal plans, collaboration between tourism officials and disaster management authorities, and the effectiveness of implemented resilience measures.

CSF 3: Enhancing Preparedness for Effective Response and Recovery

Questions within this CSF can assess the destination's readiness for response and recovery in the face of disasters. Scores can be given based on the destination's involvement in decision-making during disasters, the strength of public-private partnerships, the existence of early warning systems, and the effectiveness of response and recovery measures.

CSF 4: Investing in Resilience

This CSF focuses on the destination's investment in resilience and sustainability. Scores can be determined based on the extent to which public-sector investments are risk-informed, the allocation of resources for resilience initiatives, and the diversification of tourism products.

CSF 5: Managing Resilient and Sustainable Tourism Growth

Questions in this CSF can assess the destination's efforts to manage tourism growth in a resilient and sustainable way. Scores can be assigned based on actions taken to balance visitation

throughout the year, mitigate or adapt to the impacts of future climate change, and encourage responsible climate friendly travel.

Our objective with the Scorecard assessment is to complement the quantitative modelling approaches in MYRIAD-EU to deliver outcomes that are derived qualitatively and have the potential to drive policy for strengthening a destination's resilience against interconnected risks across multiple sectors. For example, the direct and even indirect impacts for different hazards may be quantitatively determined, however, the perception of risks and their impacts among decision makers, and the extent to which risk information based on the quantitative analysis is integrated into strategic plans, land-use plans, resource allocation, etc. can be measured qualitatively based on stakeholder surveys.

Results of the Scorecard Assessment as well as the evaluation process are captured through a prototype web-based platform and dashboard system serving as an interactive assessment tool. The web-based tool will be implemented for the Canary Island pilot for facilitating continuous scorecard assessments and the ongoing monitoring of destination resilience performance by stakeholders as seen in Figure 22. The web-based implementation of the Scorecard will also integrate quantitative outputs, including data on multi-hazard impacts from the MYRIAD-EU software, however, a seamless integration between the MYRIAD-EU Quantitative Modelling Tool and the Scorecard is not envisioned, but both contribute to the software.

Critical Success Factors (CSFs)

CSF 1

Understanding risks to tourism

CSF 2

Managing destination resilience

CSF 3

Enhancing preparedness for effective crisis response and recovery

CSF 4

Investing in resilience and sustainability

Examples of Assessment Criteria – Customizable for each Pilot in WP3

- Understanding of risks of natural disasters, climate change, public health crises, social and political unrest, cyber-security, critical infrastructure threats and economic uncertainty
- Regulations in finance, agriculture, food safety, energy and infrastructure account for destination risks
- Collaborative efforts between the tourism and energy sectors to reduce carbon footprints
- Sharing of risk information with stakeholders

- Budget, tourism development plans, zoning regulations account for managing resilience
- Cooperation between tourism officials and authorities responsible for risk management
- Extent to which resilience measures have been implemented
- Reputational risks are managed and monitored

- Minimization of disruption and losses during and after disaster events
- Availability of agreements, policies or procedures to utilize the resources of the public and private sector to improve preparedness and response activities
- Availability and implantation of preparedness and mitigation measures, and response and recovery measures
- Response plan to optimize recovery and minimize disruptions in destination lifelines and energy supply

- Public-sector investments in infrastructure and tourism projects are contingent upon them being risk informed
- Prioritization of investment in diversification of tourism product
- Level of risk transfer strategies for tourism assets
- Investments agriculture and food safety for resilient and sustainable tourism
- Support to local tourism businesses is tied to meeting sustainability standards
- Extent to which mechanisms for using income from tourism supports resilience and/or sustainability initiatives related to tourism

Figure 22: Overview of critical success factors for WP3.

4.3 Early Implementation of Risk datasets/scenarios for the pilots

4.3.1 Existing Risk Datasets: from single hazard

We have presented the hazard, exposure and vulnerability components, however there are integrated risk results that are already available for Europe, and these are important to take into account and use within the pilots and EU scale (Table 15). Only those models which do not overlap with the existing work which have already been produced for Europe which can provide benchmarks and useful outputs within MYRIAD-EU are included.

These can be used as checks for existing runs, or directly within the pilots in risk applications with overlapping hazard methods. Again, with temporal data, these events are useful multi-hazard risk scenarios for coinciding hazards such as earthquake and wind.

Table 15: Overview of available single risk models that have been sourced for MYRIAD-EU mainly for use in the financial, infrastructure and energy sectors as these are the two types of assets mostly.

Data Set/ Model	Risk Assessment Type	Types of Hazards	Risk Outputs	Resolution	Author(s)	Description
GAR15 (global system) and CDRI (2023)	Probabilistic/ Stochastic	Flood, Storm Surge, Earthquake, Volcano, Cyclone, Drought	Building Economic Damages / PML / AAL; Infrastructure Damage	Global	UNDRR, UNEP-GRID	Global Assessment of Risk - a comprehensive, global analysis of disaster risk
GEM	Probabilistic/ Stochastic	Earthquake risks	Building Economic Damages / PML / AAL	Global	Global Earthquake Model Foundation	A global, collaborative, public-private, not-for-profit organization providing earthquake risk assessment.
BN-FLEMO	Probabilistic/ Historic	Flood risks	Res/Com Economic Damages / PML / AAL	Regional	Various Authors	Flood loss estimation model for the commercial sector
JRC (Multi)	Various	Multiple risk types (e.g., floods, fires)		Global/Regional	Joint Research Centre of the European Commission	Multidisciplinary research for EU policy making, covering various risk assessments.
Alfieri et al. (2023)	Flood as per JRC	Flood Risks	EAD	Europe		

CLIMADA (Multi)	Probabilistic/ Stochastic	Climate-related risks	Building Economic Damages / PML / AAL	Global	ETH Zurich and others	Quantification of climate change impact and adaptation options.
ECA Project (World Bank) – E. Europe	Stochastic	Economic damages, other impacts	Fatalities, PMD, Economic, PML	Eastern Europe	World Bank	Europe and Central Asia - A World Bank project focusing on various risks in Eastern Europe.
Insurance Models like RMS, AIR, EQECAT, AON	Stochastic	Economic damages, insurance-related risks	Building Economic Damages / PML / AAL	Europe	Various Insurance Companies	Average Annual Losses and European Environment Agency outputs for insurance sector.
Koks and Haer (2020) – (Wind)	Probabilistic	Windstorm risks	Building AALs	Regional	Koks and Haer	Study on European windstorm risk assessment.
WRI AQUEDUCT (Flood/ Drought/ Water)	Stochastic/ Probabilistic	Flood, drought, and general water risks	Generalised Damage, EADs	Global	World Resources Institute	Global water risk mapping tool.

4.3.2 Independent (overlapping temporal) and Dependent Direct Scenario Models

Risklayer has conducted some example runs in the Danube region, which include sectoral methods for overlapping with the Agent-Based Model (ABM) for the Danube Region. However, this integration will take place in the next phase of the project. The risk analysis itself relies on the direct vulnerability function approach detailed above to generate various risk metric outputs. An illustrative example from 1940 involving a combination of flood events in Romania and Moldova, as well as an earthquake, serves as a practical application. The desired risk metrics for this scenario encompass a range of critical factors, such as the number of people exposed to damaging intensities, the economic impact, fatalities, homelessness, reconstruction costs, and sectoral impacts. This approach aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the potential consequences and vulnerabilities associated with these multi-hazard events in the specified regions.

Figure 23: Intensity Map from Kronrod et al., 2013; and the different Vrancea zone earthquake depths as an indication of why these style of events cause damage over multiple countries.

Due to the intermediate shaking nature of the event, the widespread shaking causes major issues across multi-country context as shown from the intensity map and depth in Figure 23.

Figure 24: The vulnerability functions used as part of the analyses and the damages as seen in Moldova in terms of economic damages as a % of total exposed value.

The distributed building and infrastructure damages produced through the vulnerability functions as a function of exposure types as seen in Figure 24 are then split across the ARIIO sectors to produce the needed outputs for input into the indirect damage assessment as shown in Table 16.

Table 16: Earthquake risk scenario including aftershocks – multi-sector and multi-country.

Sector	Damage	Romania mn EUR	Moldova mn EUR	Bulgaria mn EUR	NACE
S1	Agric, Forestry and Fishing	742.3	442.7	14.0	A
S2	Mining	115.1	66.2	2.1	B

S3	Manufacturing	300.2	188.0	5.9	C
S4	Electricity, Gas and Waste Management	1361.8	778.5	24.6	DE
S5	Construction	1624.2	940.4	29.7	F
S6	Commerce, hotels and restaurants	730.4	363.0	11.5	GI
S7	Transport, comm, info	1646.4	952.7	30.1	HJ
S8	Financial intermediation	317.6	190.4	6.0	K
S9	Real estate and housing services	8201.0	3312.0	126.0	L
S10	Business services	305.0	179.2	5.7	OPQR
S11	Personal services	526.1	309.0	9.8	MN
S12	Public administration	939.9	465.1	14.7	Other
Housing		8201.0	3312.0	126.0	
Non-Res		4390.0	2462.0	80.0	
Infra		4219.0	2425.0	74.0	

For a concurrent flood in the Danube Region, a number of scenarios can be chosen given the PIK Stochastic Event set for the Danube. However, for test purposes, a historical event was chosen and given which overlaps partially with the region and then the splits were produced as shown in Table 17.

Table 17: Flood risk scenario – multi-sector and multi-country.

NACE Code	POL (mn EUR)	HUN (mn EUR)	CZE (mn EUR)	HRV (mn EUR)	ROU (mn EUR)
A	476.4	94.1	23.3	25.2	206.4
B	34.7	6.8	1.7	1.8	15.0
C	132.3	26.1	6.5	7.0	57.3
D	118.0	23.3	5.8	6.2	51.1
E	596.2	117.8	58.8	31.5	258.2
F	66.7	13.2	3.3	3.5	28.9
G	77.3	15.3	3.8	4.1	33.5
H	404.5	79.9	52.4	21.4	175.2
I	22.2	4.4	1.1	1.2	9.6
J	50.7	10.0	2.5	2.7	21.9
K	32.0	6.3	1.6	1.7	13.9
L	649.2	128.3	31.8	34.3	281.2
M	30.7	6.1	1.5	1.6	13.3
N	36.1	7.1	1.8	1.9	15.6
O	110.9	21.9	5.4	5.9	48.1
P	28.1	5.5	1.4	1.5	12.2
Q	13.0	2.6	0.6	0.7	5.6
R	9.8	1.9	0.5	0.5	4.2
S	6.2	1.2	0.3	0.3	2.7
T	0	0	0	0	0
U	0	0	0	0	0

From these tables, the Danube Pilot has run the indirect impacts in order to examine the sectoral damage and loss influence.

4.4 Development of Indirect Hazard and Risk Methodologies and Datasets

Total impacts of hazards depend on indirect impacts of hazards in addition to direct impacts. Indirect impacts of hazards result from effects from direct exposure to a hazard impacting the provision of goods or services, which in turn affect the ability of connected parts of the system to function. A concrete example could be local flooding reducing agricultural production, increasing the prices of agricultural goods, increasing food prices. Through trade, these effects may be transmitted locally or globally depending on the significance of the shortfall of production. The persistence of impacts on a European or global scale depends on the abilities of the impacted region, but also other regions, to make up for shortfalls in local production.

As part of Task 5.3, the impact of indirect effects both inter-regionally as well as between sectors within the affected region are being investigated using a suite of existing macroeconomic models. Existing models within the MYRIAD-EU project are a macro economic agent-based model (Poledna et al. 2023), an integrated assessment meta-model used to investigate dynamic adaptive policy pathways (Haasnoot et al., 2013), the computable general equilibrium model GRACE (Aaheim et al. 2018), and empirical and machine learning methods. Furthermore, indirect effects will be described qualitatively in the Canary Islands pilot. The Multiregional Impact Assessment model MRIA will also be applied to investigate the indirect effects on a Europe wide scale.

In addition to the direct impacts of a hazard event such as physical damage to buildings and infrastructure or loss of life, hazards can affect the productivity of economic and ecosystem activities during the event. Furthermore, the direct impacts and disruptions can indirectly affect the provision of goods or services, which in turn affect the ability of connected parts of the system to function. These cascading impacts contribute to the overall systemic risks associated with hazards (Sillmann et al., 2022). Here we focus on these indirect effects of direct impacts, as their contribution to the final effect of a hazard on economic output and welfare can be large both in their magnitude and in spatial and temporal extent, affecting a wider area than that directly impacted for a longer time (Meyer et al., 2013; Przulski and Hallegatte, 2011).

We aim to investigate indirect effects from three perspectives: interregional, intersectoral, and intertemporal. The interregional aspect of indirect effects describes to what degree the spatial extents of impacts propagate from the directly affected site of a hazard. Most commonly this is driven by trade relationships between businesses in the affected area and those outside, but could also be the result of a drought event causing the depletion of water reservoirs that supply other regions or heavy rainfall events on the upper reaches of a river flow causing flooding downstream in addition to local impacts. The intersectoral aspect of indirect effects describes how impacts cross boundaries between sectors. In the realm of economics this involves supply chains between economic sectors. For example, a local flood could reduce agricultural production, increasing the prices of agricultural goods, increasing food prices, crossing sectoral boundaries from the agricultural sector to the food processing industry and households. The intertemporal aspect, finally, relates to the time delay of indirect effects including both the time required for recovery of destroyed physical assets and possible persistent shifts in supply chains. Both the interregional and intersectoral indirect effects are exasperated by long value chains. Recent efforts to make production more local have not been sufficient to reverse the long-running trend toward more globally integrated supply chains (Qiu et al., 2023).

Lacking a counterfactual world without a given hazard event, models are used to estimate the direct impacts and indirect effects. Most commonly, input-output, computable general equilibrium, or hybrid models have been applied for this. However, the different models provide widely different estimates of the impacts of a given hazard event, even in cases where the same direct impact is evaluated. These differences in outcomes are explained by the assumptions that go into the construction of the models. While input-output models specify strict production relationships, computable general equilibrium and hybrid models allow for more flexibility to adjust to limited supply of a certain good. Consequently, indirect effects may be overestimated in an input-output model as a missing input may reduce production in large swaths of the economy, while computational general equilibrium models may underestimate the duration of indirect effects as the assumption of market equilibria with immediate adjustment ignores the time it takes economic

actors to find new suppliers or to change manufacturing processes following a shortage (Koks et al., 2016).

Given this wide range in estimates from different modelling approaches it is worthwhile to further compare estimates of total impacts for specified similar direct impacts of hazard events, and thereby to compare how indirect effects are represented across a wide range of different modelling approaches and in what range they may be expected to be in reality. Here we benefit from the broad range of modelling expertise present in the MYRIAD-EU pilots. Each of the project partners heading the individual pilots bring with them expertise in certain methods. These range from a computationally expensive ABM to qualitative storyline approaches. As a first step to comparing the outcomes, we provide an overview of these modelling approaches below.

4.4.1 Agent Based Macro Models

In ABMs each actor is simulated individually. In the application to economics, actors are individual humans, households, or firms. These types of models are most often applied to small contained systems such as a single neighbourhood. In the case of agent based macro models, this approach is applied to macro economic systems, such as an entire country. ABMs are suited to modelling indirect effects as they are disaggregated, allowing representation of the behaviour of individual actors in response to the hazard event itself or to an induced supply shortage. These responses can be heterogeneous, reflecting differing abilities of actors to respond to events and expectations formed about future events.

The model to be used in the Danube pilot is based on an ABM of the Austrian economy (Poledna et al., 2023) and its customised version for assessment of economic consequences of flood damages (Bachner et al., 2023). The model resolves all actors (households and firms) in the economy for which observations are available in national accounting databases. This allows for the determination of short- to medium-term macroeconomic and sector-level or industry-specific effects of shocks or policies.

The model is intended to overcome the drawbacks of other ABMs, i.e. too many degrees of freedom allowing overmatching of data and lacking forecasting power of macro data (while ABMs have been used to replicate stylised behaviours found in macro data (boom-bust cycles, etc.) they by and large can not predict them).

The model is based around four key approaches: “(1) building an ABM around publicly available macro and microdata of a small open economy, (2) disciplining the individual behaviour of agents (consumers, firms, and banks) through simple heuristics that are calibrated using microdata, (3) using a simple adaptive learning model of expectations through the learning of optimal autoregressive (AR) forecasting rules consistent with macro data, and (4) adopting an empirical validation strategy based on out-of-sample forecasting of macro variables. Furthermore, our detailed ABM contains all sectors of an open economy and can therefore be used for policy analysis.” (Poledna et al., 2023)

The model is solved numerically starting from a chosen year and quarter of observation, to which all model state and flow variables are calibrated. The model is then solved recursively quarter by quarter, up to five years ahead.

The MYRIAD-EU project is structured around five pilot regions: Canary Islands, Veneto, Danube, North Sea, and Scandinavia. Each pilot region is investigated by a different group of researchers using differing methods to investigate the effects of multiple hazards and risks. Existing models within the MYRIAD-EU project are a macro economic agent-based model (Poledna et al., 2023), an integrated assessment meta-model used to investigate dynamic adaptive policy pathways (Haasnoot, 2013), the computable general equilibrium model GRACE (Aaheim et al., 2018), and empirical and machine learning methods. Indirect effects will be described qualitatively in the Canary Islands pilot. Furthermore, the Multiregional Impact Assessment model MRIA (Koks & Thissen, 2016) will be applied to investigate the indirect effects on a Europe wide scale.

4.4.2 Dynamic Adaptive Policy Pathways applied to Integrated Assessment Meta Models

Dynamic Adaptive Policy Pathways (DAPP) is a framework approach to deal with the uncertainty about future outcomes of policy actions and development in natural systems (Haasnoot et al., 2013). DAPP prescribes the evaluation of a multitude of policy options over time, instead of a single policy path, as would be the case in a pure optimisation procedure, or single policy evaluation. Crucially these paths are evaluated simultaneously with a perspective to switch between paths at points in the future. This is a beneficial property in the context of indirect effects, as their impacts can depend on policy choices over time. In particular, the time to recover from an event and the displacement of economic activity may both be affected by the timing of policy choices.

An IAMM is an integrated model of simplified emulations of more complex impact assessment models. It serves two main purposes: (1) allowing for the integration of multiple different models into one modelling framework to increase uniformity between different modelling components; and (2) increasing the modelling speed (Haasnoot et al., 2014). Particularly the latter is needed to achieve the computational performance required to apply the DAPP framework, which necessitates a large number of model evaluations. Metamodels aim to mimic behaviour of more complex models simulating cause-effect chains. As such, they are broadly seen as statistically inferred modelling approaches, which sometimes also include theory-motivated phenomenological insights (Davis & Bigelow, 2003). These models can also be extended by decision rules governing response choices of human decision-makers from a prescribed policy portfolio (Schlumberger et al. 2023 in review). The decision rules are used to explore the outcome space of policy choices, akin to a stress test. IAMMs have been used for local (e.g. airport policy design (Kwakkel et al., 2010)), regional (e.g. river basin scale (Ward et al., 2011)) or national research problems (e.g. The Netherlands, (Haasnoot et al., 2014)) and on different temporal scales reaching from 10-day timesteps to annual temporal resolution.

In the North Sea pilot an initial application of impact models for the three sectors shipping, agriculture, and residential are incorporated in a conceptual river model (the Waas-MR model). The model describes a synthetic small region of 75 square kilometres capturing properties of a generic river flow in the Netherlands based on the Waal, a river reach in the Rhine delta of the Netherlands (Haasnoot et al., 2013). It explores the performance of different policy alternatives across a planning horizon of 100 years with a temporal resolution of 10-days and a spatial resolution of 100 m (Schlumberger et al. 2023 in review). It is planned to extend the initial application to a case study of the Netherlands. In this extension subregions could be modelled as interrelated subsystems with independent decision makers.

4.4.3 Computational General Equilibrium Models

Computational General Equilibrium (CGE) models are numerical economic optimisation models that describe the change in production in an economy based on the balancing of supply and demand in different economic sectors and economic regions or countries. These models follow economic theory assuming consumers maximise utility, firms maximise profits, incomes and expenditures of all economic agents are balanced as are production and consumption of goods and services. With regard to the indirect effects this implies that the modelled economy will adjust immediately to changed demand due to the hazard event, as the economic underpinnings of the model prescribe frictionless markets. This may cause CGE models to underestimate the duration of the effects of an impact (Koks et al., 2016). In the model context, firms are able to instantaneously ramp up production in response to increased demand, while in reality they are limited by existing production capacity. Increasing production may involve building of new factories, procuring production equipment and hiring workers. All these activities take time to accomplish in the real world, but are abstracted away in the model, allowing for an instantaneous response.

In MYRIAD-EU the CGE model GRACE is used, operated by the members of the Scandinavian pilot. This is a CGE model conceptually capable of representing trade and production of an arbitrary amount of regions. The GRACE model is calibrated based on annual observations in the GTAP database (Aguiar et al., 2022). The limiting factor is the availability of input output data to specify the model relationships. Similarly, the model can be run with different numbers of sectors included. The baseline version of the model (Aaheim et al., 2018) includes separate production of

consumption goods, primary energy, goods and services other than agriculture and primary energy, electricity, non-fossil electricity production, and fossil electricity production for each region. The model further includes regional capital stocks and investments as well as regional households driving demand and investment. Investment across regions is possible, balancing the regional returns. Furthermore, the GRACE model is constructed in a set of nonlinear inequalities to reach zero profit, market clearing and income balance conditions. The solution from the GRACE model includes various activity levels, price indexes and income.

4.4.4 Empirical and Machine Learning Methods

Neural networks will be constructed for variables of interest in specific sectors. In the environmental sector these are water quality and vegetation stress. While in the tourism sector anomalies in tourist numbers, GDP, and disaster deaths will be considered. Initially the neural nets describing each of the sectors will be separate models, if possible they will be combined at a later point to allow the investigation of intersectoral indirect effects. The models will initially further be specific to hazards. One model for heat, one for floods and high precipitation. The nets will either be constructed as a constrained graph, where connections between nodes are set up explicitly by the modeller, or as a dense neural network (with initially all nodes being connected) where the strength of the connections is then learned from the data. The models will be both spatially and temporally explicit allowing for the investigation of spatial and temporal indirect effects within the Veneto region. Given that these models will be based on observational data, spatial and temporal extents of indirect effects will not be subject to theory induced biases described above.

For water quality the nodes of the net are fed by data from observation stations along the river flow and environmental data (temperature, precipitation). With the trained net it will be possible to evaluate the expected river quality under different environmental conditions, including climate projections.

For vegetation stress the nodes of the net would be fed by remote sensing spatio-temporal vegetation stress and environmental data. With the trained net it will be possible to evaluate the expected vegetation stress under different environmental conditions, including climate projections.

For the socio-economic variables the nodes of the net would be fed by data on tourism numbers, GDP, and local health outcomes. Data on the socio-economic variables is most challenging to acquire, especially due to the coarse reporting of socio-economic data.

4.4.5 Descriptive Qualitative Methods

Building a model always requires simplification of the real system under consideration. The degree of simplification differs between the different approaches. This trade-off can be avoided to some degree by the choice not to model and quantify system interactions, but rather to describe connections in a qualitative way. In the Canary Islands pilot a multi-level strategy is applied to describe the collaborative system focused on the tourism industry. In a high-level approach the system is described conceptually as a place where residents and visitors share common resources and compete for land development. The objective of the collaborative system definition is to describe the vulnerability of the tourism sector to direct impacts from natural hazards, but also to indirect impacts of hazards in other sectors. Simultaneously, in a bottom up approach the welfare of residents depending on the tourism industry is also investigated. Certain aspects of the system are described spatially including maps of potentially affected areas, and description of direct and indirect impacts this would have.

4.4.6 Multiregional Impact Assessment Model (MRIA)

The multiregional impact assessment model (Koks & Thissen, 2016) is a recursive dynamic multiregional supply-use model based on input output modelling combined with linear optimisation methods. The model covers the European region at a NUTS 2 level built on the EUREGIO database (Thissen et al., 2018). Production technologies relating inputs to outputs are specific to the individual regions. Damaging production capacity or productivity in a region causes production shifts to other regions or to less efficient production within regions. These shifts in production to unaffected regions are a result of the linear optimisation of production and enable regions not

affected by a hazard to benefit from the increased demand during the reconstruction phase. Consequently, this model is very suited to the assessment of interregional and intersectoral indirect effects. The temporal aspect of impacts, the time it takes for damages to be repaired, is an external input of the model.

4.4.7 Comparison of Modelling Approaches

We compare the presented modelling approaches along six properties. These are the spatial and temporal resolution, the sectoral and regional coverage, time horizon, and the computation speed. Each of these properties is assigned a value on a five point scale shown in Table 18. In addition the differences in how the different approaches represent indirect effects with regard to intersectoral, interregional and intertemporal propagation of direct impacts. The numerical values assigned to different modes of representation are shown in Table 19. The classification of indirect effects representation is within the context of the coverage of a given model. A model with only two sectors can score highly on the representation of intersectoral indirect effects if the link between the two sectors is especially detailed.

Table 18: Model comparison criteria for general descriptives.

	1	2	3	4	5
Spatial Resolution	Global	National	Coarse Grid / NUTS 2	Fine Grid / NUTS 3	Household
Temporal Resolution	Multiyear timestep	Yearly	Coarse sub year	Monthly	Daily
Sectoral Coverage	Single production function	Single explicit sector others aggregated	2-6 Sectors	Single digit industry identifier 7-20 Sectors	Two digit industry identifier >20 Sectors
Regional Coverage	Single subnational region	national	multinational region	multi continent	whole globe
Time/Prediction Horizon	sub year	single year	decade	century	centuries
Computational Requirements	long on super-computer	fast on super-computer		long on laptop	fast on laptop

Table 19: Comparison criteria for indirect effects.

	1	2	3	4	5
Intersectoral indirect effects	only direct effects		linear sectoral dependencies		non-linear sectoral dependencies

Interregional indirect effects	only local effects		simple trade or physical links between regions		detailed trade and physical feedbacks
Intertemporal indirect effects	only contemporary effects		simple lagged effects		fully dynamics representation of effects

For each of the modelling approaches introduced above, we assigned three values. These are the minimum and maximum that could be expected to be covered by a given modelling approach and how a model would be used in its default settings. These values are plotted as a spider web diagram with the default settings plotted as solid lines and the range of possibility with each approach are shown as shaded areas. Figure 25 shows the general descriptives of the modelling approaches. There is a clear trade-off between spatial resolution and regional coverage as well as between the temporal resolution and the time horizon. In addition, the combination of resolution and coverage poses a trade-off with computational requirements for quantitative methods. A further limit to high spatial and temporal resolution of models is the availability of suitable data for calibration covering multiple regions in a harmonised way with detail on individual sectors.

Figure 25: Comparison of the modelling approaches along the six dimensions of spatial and temporal resolution, sectoral and regional coverage, time horizon and computational speed. The solid lines show the default settings of the modelling approaches while the shadings indicate the range or possibility with each approach. The legend for the values can be found in Table 1.

As with the general descriptives, the models differ in their representation of indirect effects shown in Figure 26. The models developed with the goal of explaining or predicting shifts in trading

patterns, GRACE and MRIA, excel at the representation of indirect effects. Similarly, the ABM, IAMM, and GRACE model are designed to correctly represent intersectoral effects. However, they include different sets of assumptions in their design, affecting the representation of intertemporal indirect effects. As a result of the assumed perfectly functioning markets with instantaneous adjustment to disruptions, CGE models tend to underestimate indirect effects of an impact compared to input-output based models such as MRIA (Koks et al., 2016).

Figure 26: Comparison of the abilities of the modelling approaches to represent indirect effects of extreme events across sectors, across regions, and across time. The solid lines show the default settings of the modelling approaches while the shadings indicate the range or possibility with each approach. The legend for the values can be found in Table 21: Comparison criteria for indirect effects.

4.4.8 Outlook

The next steps in the assessment of how the different models handle indirect effects and how these differences affect the projected magnitude and spatio-temporal extent of indirect effects is to evaluate a set of common hazard scenarios in each of the models. The scenarios will be evaluated in both current and future conditions. Future conditions will be described by RCPs and SSPs chosen according to the needs of users in the pilots. The scenarios will be based on hazards described within the pilots. The magnitude of the hazards will be derived from direct impact data collected in Work Package 5 of the MYRIAD-EU project, in collaboration with the pilots. In order for the scenarios to be evaluated in each of the models, they will have to be aggregated to the spatial, sectoral, and temporal resolution of the models. As these vary between the models, equivalent specifications will have to be found that describe the direct impact of a given hazard scenario at different resolutions. Only if this can be achieved, will it be possible to fairly compare the outputs of the models.

5 Conclusion and Next Steps

This report has focused on tools and methods for developing multi-hazard and multi-risk scenarios, focusing on their applicability to the five pilot regions within Europe. We have outlined the requirements for generating comprehensive multi-risk scenarios, including the development of dynamic feedbacks between risk drivers, clear definitions of key indicators and risk metrics, and defining impact-relevant threshold parameters. The deliverable has set out the interim hazard, exposure and risk sets to be used as part of the multi-hazard and multi-risk scenarios. The work contributes to generating and quantifying hazard events and risks, ensuring these scenarios are realistic, detailed, and can begin to be tailored to the specific requirements of the five pilot regions for use in software risk outputs as well as additional pilot outputs.

Interaction with other work packages

Risklayer's work in WP5 is also directly influenced by the developments in WP4, which focuses on identifying and understanding the dynamic feedbacks between risk drivers. The empirical evidence and functions developed in WP4 are crucial for WP5, particularly in Task 5.2, where Risklayer incorporates these dynamics and feedbacks into risk quantification models. The development of tools and methods in WP5 is driven by the requirements of the pilot core user groups and stakeholders through the iterative process described in WP3. This collaborative approach ensures that the tools and methods developed are aligned with the practical needs and insights gained from the pilot stakeholders.

The outcomes and risk scenarios developed by Risklayer in WP5 can inform WP6, such as the identification of threshold events to be incorporated into DRM pathways for those pilot regions following the DAPP-MR approach. Finally, the datasets and methods developed for generating multi-hazard event sets as shown above in WP5 are informed by the findings and data collected in WP1, as well as the framework and methodology outlined in WP2. The diagnostic work in WP1 lays the foundation for understanding the current state of knowledge and data availability, which is then expanded upon in WP5 for the development of realistic multi-hazard scenarios.

The Europe-wide datasets provide a first-pass model for most applications and are enough to often ask more detailed questions or plan a modelling framework at the pilot level. For direct risk this is being examined in the Canary Islands, in the Danube region and in Veneto. Examples were shown as to potential damages from scenarios.

Next Steps

This work aligns with the project's broader vision of employing a multi-sectoral, multi-risk approach through disaster risk management strategies that consider trade-offs and synergies across sectors, hazards, and scales.

The next steps include the integration of some selected models, data and methodologies into a software platform under development by Risklayer, in line with the pilots. In Task 5.3, the evaluation focuses on the indirect risks that span across different sectors and regions, derived from the event sets applied in the five pilot studies. Subsequently, Task 5.4 involves the development of new software that integrates the methodological advancements made in Tasks 4.3, 5.1, and 5.2.

During the initial phase of design and development, which is the phase covered by this report, we created preliminary versions of the methodologies and instruments for generating multi-hazard events along with their direct and indirect risks, also supplying the Pilots with initial event sets. In the phase of Testing and Refinement, which is the next phase of the project, we will enhance these methodologies and instruments, taking into account the outcomes of the tests conducted in the Pilots. In the Finalisation phase, we will incorporate these tools into the comprehensive software package, including an interface that will enable users to explore various multi-risk and multi-hazard scenarios across different locations in Europe. It will also provide information on available exposure data that can be utilised to populate the risk scenarios.

Limitations, Issues, and Data Requirements

Creating plausible temporal sequences for hazard interactions and accurately assigning return periods to events is complex. Modelling damaging events and dealing with the dynamic nature of hazards adds significant uncertainty. Establishing impact-relevant thresholds, predicting future changes in vulnerability, and assessing impacts of events like volcanic eruptions is challenging. Obtaining precise data for exposure analysis, like time-of-day data for tourist patterns, is not always straightforward. Quantifying the effectiveness of Disaster Risk Reduction measures is complicated due to policy shifts and complex interactions between sectors and hazards.

The report relies on high-quality data for exposure, hazard and vulnerability from various sources, and stresses the need for tailored data sets for the different sectors involved in the MYRIAD-EU project. The data must be adaptable to changing conditions and sufficiently detailed to capture the dynamics of multi-hazard risks both for current and future conditions.

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Appendix A: Exposure Datasets

Table 20: Overview of available population datasets.

Data Set/Model	Asset Type	Resolution	Author(s)	Description
GHS-POP (2023A vers)	Population Grid	Multitemporal	JRC	The GHSL Data Package 2023 includes multitemporal products from 1975 through 2020, and future projections for 2025 and 2030. It offers insights into human presence using data from Sentinel-2, Landsat, and global DEM data. Including the ENACT dataset for usage in temporal settings (day/night, and monthly)
HRSL (30m)	Population Grid	30m	Facebook	The High Resolution Settlement Layer (HRSL) from Facebook provides human population distribution estimates for the year 2015 at a resolution of 30m, based on recent census data and high-resolution satellite imagery.
Kontur (400m)	Population Grid	400m	Kontur	Kontur Population dataset uses H3 hexagons to represent population counts. It is based on GHSL data, Facebook population data (HRSL), Microsoft Building Footprint, Land Information New Zealand, and Copernicus Global Land Service data.
GEOSTAT	Population Grid	1km	EC	GEOSTAT provides population data on a 1km square grid. The 2021 Census presented key census topics on an EU-wide 1 km square grid, allowing for flexible cross-border analysis.
EUROSTAT CENSUS GRID 2021	Census Data	1km	EC	The 2021 Census data are available on an EU-wide 1 km square grid, offering a more detailed and flexible analysis tailored to research or policy needs.
GFZ	Exposure Data	NUTS3	Steinhausen, M.; Schröter, K.; Lüdtkke, S.; Drews, M.	European exposure data for BN-FLEMO models, including European asset map, residential building areas, and flood experience data.

WSF-3D Pop (12m-90m)	Building Data	90m	DLR	Quantification of buildings' average height, total volume, area, and fraction, using satellite imagery and radar data.
Landscan (1km)	Population Grid	30 arc-seconds	Oak Ridge National Laboratory	Global model for population distribution based on land cover, slope, proximity to roads, and settlement locations.
WorldPop (100m), top-down constrained and unconstrained /GRID3	Population Data	High resolution (100m)	Tatem et al. (2023)	Data on population distributions and characteristics at high spatial resolution.
CIESIN GPW	Population Data	Various	CIESIN	Population estimates and densities for 1990 and 1995 on a 2.5' grid, adjusted to match United Nations national population estimates.
HANZE v2.0 1870-2020 (100m)	Land Cover/Use, Population, GDP, Assets	100m	Paprotny et al. (2023)	High-resolution maps of land cover/use, population, GDP, and fixed assets for 42 countries in Europe from 1870 to 2020.
Data for Good Mobility Data	Population movement	Various resolutions	Facebook	https://dataforgood.facebook.com/dfg/tools/movement-range-maps Mobility data during COVID - however other datasets exist
Maddison (2008) and country statistical offices	Population	Country	Maddison (2008) and country statistical offices	
Google Mobility Data	Population movement	Various resolutions	Google	https://www.google.com/covid19/mobility/data_documentation.html?hl=en These reports detail the movement trends as Over time arranged by geographical areas and classified into various categories of places, such as shops and leisure spaces, supermarkets and pharmacies, parks, public transport stations, workplaces and residential areas.

SERA-EU	Exposure Models	Admin Level 1	Vitor Silva, Venetia Despotaki (GEM Foundation)	Development of exposure and vulnerability models for seismic risk reduction strategies in Europe, based on the latest national housing census data.
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Figure 27: Map of spatial distribution of population per square kilometre based on the EUROSTAT Census Grid 2021.

Table 21: Overview of available exposure datasets.

Data Set/Model	Asset Type	Economic Value	Resolution	Author(s)	Description
GHS-BUILT-V	Residential Buildings	No	30m raster	European Commission	Global Human Settlement layer with building information for exposure assessment
WSF 3D	Buildings, Other Infra	No	10m-30m raster	World Settlement Footprint	3D information on global settlement extent

SERA	Residential, Industrial, Commercial	Yes	Mostly admin zone	SERA Project Consortium	Seismology and Earthquake Engineering Research Infrastructure Alliance for Europe
HANZE	Infrastructure + Buildings (Residential, Commercial)	Yes	100m raster	Project HANZE	Hazard ANalysis ZonE: energy grid-focused dataset
EUBUCCO	Buildings	No, mostly	Building by building	EUBUCCO Consortium	European Building Cultural COntext dataset
OAM	Various Assets	No	1km raster	OpenAerial Map Contributors	Provides openly available aerial imagery for different uses, including risk assessment
BUILT-C MSZ	Residential Buildings, Infrastructure	No	10m Raster	Consortium of European Seismological Agencies	Building typology and vulnerability classification for seismic risk assessment
GFZ	Residential Buildings	Yes	Polygon (NUTS3)		Residential Building Stock
Daniell and Schaefer (2014)	Capital Stock (Infrastructure and Buildings)	Yes	Polygon and 1km raster		Eastern Europe Capital Stock
PWT 10.01 (2023)	Capital Stock	Yes	Single value per country	Groningen Growth Center	Provides country level metrics
Global ML Footprints	Building Footprints	No	Individual Building Footprints	Microsoft	A non-exhaustive set of building polygons.
Google Buildings	Building Footprints	No			Single footprints for a number of areas with close to full coverage
TABULA	Building Typologies and Energy Standards	Partial		Consortium	
ENPER-EXIST	Building Typologies and Energy Standards	Partial		Consortium	
CORINE Land Cover	Land Use, Infrastructure	No	Vector and 100m raster	European Environment Agency	Provides information on the land cover of Europe (44 thematic classes) for environmental assessment purposes, updated every six years
Urban Atlas	Urban Infrastructure	No	Varies	European Environment Agency	Detailed vector data for large urban areas in Europe, useful for assessing urban exposure

France TOPO3D	Terrain, Buildings	No	1m-5m raster, Polygons	National Institute of Geographic and Forest Information (IGN France)	A 3D representation of the French territory including detailed topography and building information
SwissBUIL DINGS3D	Buildings	Yes	Building by building	Swisstopo	Detailed 3D model of buildings across Switzerland for precise exposure assessment
INSPIRE Geoportal	Various Assets	No	Varies	INSPIRE Directive	Pan-European spatial data infrastructure for sharing environmental spatial information among public sector organisations
LUCAS	Land Use/Cover Area frame statistical Survey	No	Points	Eurostat	A harmonised survey providing statistically representative data on land cover and use across the EU
GEM Building Taxonomy	Buildings	Yes	Varies	Global Earthquake Model Foundation	A global framework for classifying buildings in terms of their vulnerability to earthquakes.
Global Human Settlemen t Layer (GHSL)	Residential Areas	No	2m raster to 1km	European Commission , JRC	Provides global spatial information about human settlements over time.
OpenStree tMap (OSM)	Various Assets	No	Building by building to various scales	OpenStreet Map Contributors	A collaborative project to create a free editable map of the world, contains data on roads, railways, waterways, and buildings.
Paul et al. 2022	Various Assets	Yes	30m raster	Paul et al.	Admin Level datasets of structural, non-structural and contents data for different wall typologies specific to earthquake, with residential, commercial, and industrial buildings covered.

Dutch Large Scale Topograph y (BRT)/ BAG Delft3D	Terrain, Infrastructu re	No	1m vector	Kadaster Netherlands and Delft	A highly detailed topographic database of the Netherlands, used for urban planning and risk management
Portugues e Cartograp hy	Terrain, Buildings	Yes	Varies	Direção- Geral do Território (DGT)	National mapping agency provides detailed maps and geographic information of Portugal

German ATKIS	All Assets including buildings	No	1m-25m raster/vector	Bundesamt für Kartographie und Geodäsie (BKG)	Standardized geoinformation for Germany used in planning and environmental protection
Italian Geoportale Nazionale	Population, Housing	No	Varies	Istituto Nazionale di Statistica (ISTAT)	Demographic and housing census data providing socio-economic and dwelling characteristics in Italy
UK Ordnance Survey MasterMap	Various Assets	Yes, when joined	Up to 1m vector	Ordnance Survey	A comprehensive, high-resolution map database of Great Britain, detailing land cover and infrastructure assets
Danish Building & Dwelling Register	Buildings, Dwellings	Yes, when joined	Building by building	Danish Geodata Agency	A registry containing information about all buildings and dwellings in Denmark, including use and occupancy
National Inventory of Landscapes in Sweden (NILS)	Natural Assets, Landscapes	No	100m raster	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences	A database aimed at assessing the state and changes in Sweden's landscapes, including valuable habitats and biodiversity
Spanish Cadastre	Buildings, Land	Yes	Parcel level	Dirección General del Catastro	The official register of the property value of buildings and land in Spain, used for taxation and urban planning
Polish Topographic Database (BDOT10k)	Various Assets	No	10m vector	Head Office of Geodesy and Cartography	Detailed topographic data including buildings, land use, and transportation networks in Poland
Norwegian National Geo-Infrastructure (GEOVEKST)	Various Assets	Yes	Varies	Norwegian Mapping Authority	A collaborative initiative to develop and maintain high-quality geospatial data in Norway
Czech Geoportal	Various Assets	Yes	Varies	Czech Office for Surveying, Mapping, and Cadastre	Centralised portal for geospatial information in the Czech Republic, including cadastral, topographic, and environmental data.
Finnish Topographic Database (KMTK)	Various Assets	No	1m-10m vector	National Land Survey of Finland	Comprehensive database including terrain models, buildings, and infrastructure data for Finland.
Separate Maps for Wallonie, Flanders and Brussels	Infrastructure, Buildings	No	Up to 1m vector	Respective Geoportals	The base map of Flanders, Brussels and Wallonie provides detailed geographical data of buildings, parcels, roads, waterways, and more.

Lithuanian Spatial Information Portal (LSIP)	Various Assets	No	Varies	National Land Service under the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania	A portal for spatial information, including cadastre, topography, and land cover data in Lithuania.
Cadastral Parcel Information System of Turkey (TAKBIS)	Land Parcels	Yes	Parcel level	General Directorate of Land Registry and Cadastre of Turkey	An extensive system providing detailed cadastral information for land parcels across Turkey.
GRECIA Project Database	Residential, Infrastructure	Yes	Building by building	GRECIA Consortium	Focuses on seismic exposure and vulnerability assessment of Greek building stock.
Austria Address Register	Buildings, Dwellings	Yes	Address level	Statistik Austria	Contains addresses and, in many cases, links to building polygons for the entire country.
Geo-Information of Natural Hazards (GIN)	Various Assets	No	Varies	Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN), Switzerland	Includes data on flood hazards, landslides, and other natural risks.
Estonian Address Data System (ADS)	Buildings, Infrastructure	Yes	Building by building	Estonian Land Board	Provides detailed address data linked to buildings and other structures.
Slovak Geoportal	Various Assets	No	Varies	Geodesy, Cartography and Cadastre Authority of Slovak Republic	Centralised access to a wide range of spatial data including cadastre, topography, and environmental datasets.
MALTA Map Server	Various Assets	Yes	Varies	Planning Authority, Malta	Provides detailed geographical information systems (GIS) data for Malta, including zoning, land use, and building data.
Cyprus Integrated Land Information System	Land Parcels, Infrastructure	Yes	Parcel level	Department of Lands and Surveys, Cyprus	Centralised land information system offering detailed data on parcels, property values, and infrastructure.
Ireland's PRIME2	Land Parcels	Yes	Parcel level	Property Registration Authority, Ireland	A national dataset providing detailed information on property boundaries and ownership.

Spain SIOSE	Land Use, Infrastructure	No	Varies	National Geographic Institute (IGN) Spain	Provides detailed land use and land cover information for the whole of Spain.
Portugal DGT	Various Assets	No	Varies	Directorate- General for Territory (DGT), Portugal	A comprehensive dataset including a variety of geospatial information on Portuguese territory.
Latvia's Geoportal	Various Assets	No	Varies	Latvian Geospatial Information Agency	Offers a wide range of geospatial data, including topography, cadastre, and environmental datasets.
Hungary's FÖMI	Various Assets	No	Varies	Institute of Geodesy, Cartography and Remote Sensing (FÖMI), Hungary	Provides access to a variety of geospatial information including land administration and environmental data.
Bulgaria's Cadastre and Property Register	Land Parcels, Buildings	Yes	Building and parcel level	Agency for Geodesy, Cartography and Cadastre, Bulgaria	Contains detailed records of properties, their associated land parcels, and buildings for the whole country.
Sweden's Lantmäter iet	Various Assets	Yes	Varies	Swedish Mapping, Cadastral and Land Registration Authority	Offers extensive geographical and land survey data, including buildings, infrastructure, and land use.
GeoDanm ark	Various Assets	Yes	Varies	The Danish Geodata Agency	A detailed spatial data collection that covers the entire Danish territory, including Greenland and the Faroe Islands.

Balkan GeoPortal	Various Assets	No	Varies	South-East Europe (SEE) project	A collaborative effort to integrate and share geospatial information across the Balkan region.
Serbian Real Estate Cadastre	Buildings, Infrastructure	Yes	Building by building	Republic Geodetic Authority of Serbia	Provides comprehensive information on real estate, including buildings and infrastructure with economic valuation.
Croatian Cadastre	Land Parcels, Buildings	Yes	Parcel level	State Geodetic Administration of Croatia	Detailed cadastre data including property boundaries, buildings, and land use.
Bosnian Real Estate Registration	Land Parcels, Buildings	Yes	Varies	Federation Administration for Geodetic and Real Property Affairs	Contains real estate information for the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina, part of the country's dual entities.
National Cadastre & Mapping Agency S.A. (NCMA)	Various Assets	Yes	Varies	NCMA, Greece	Offers detailed cadastre and mapping data for Greece, including the northern regions which form part of the Balkans.
North Macedonia's Agency for Real Estate Cadastre	Buildings, Land Parcels	Yes	Building and parcel level	Agency for Real Estate Cadastre of North Macedonia	Provides detailed information on real estate, important for risk and exposure assessment in the country.
Albanian National Agency of Territorial Planning	Land Use, Infrastructure	Yes	Varies	National Agency of Territorial Planning, Albania	Offers planning and territorial data, including urban plans and infrastructural information for exposure modeling.

Figure 28: Example map of buildings footprints in the Netherlands (left) and a colour graded representation of average building height per raster cell.

Table 22: Overview of available infrastructure exposure datasets.

Data Set/Model	Asset Type	Resolution	Author(s)	Description
Critical Infrastructure Spatial Index	Multiple CI Systems (transport, energy, telecom, etc.)	0.10 × 0.10 and 0.25 × 0.25 deg	Arderne et al. (2020)	Harmonised global spatial dataset for CI systems representation.
HARCI-EU (HARmonized grids of Critical Infrastructures in EUrope)	CI in transport, energy, industry, social sectors	1 km ²	[Not specified]	Integrates geospatial and statistical data for major CIs in Europe.
Global Roads Inventory Project (GRIP)	Roads	5 arcminutes (~8x8km)	Meijer, J.R., Huijbregts, M.A.J., Schotten, C.G.J., Schipper, A.M.	Global and regional roads dataset for environmental and biodiversity assessments.
EUROSTAT Transport Database	Transportation Infrastructure	Network based	EUROSTAT	Transport-related data, including infrastructure, across Europe.
OECD Infrastructure Investment	Inland infrastructure (road, rail, waterways, etc.)	Mostly country based	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)	Covers spending on new transport construction and the improvement of existing networks.
Open Infrastructure Map	Various (power, water, telecom, etc.)	Uses OSM, but is vector format mostly.	[Not specified]	A map showing various infrastructure elements globally, including in Europe.

European Data Portal - Water	Water data	Network based	[Not specified]	Over 25,000 datasets related to water, including hydrological data, water chemistry, supply plans, etc.
Mining Sites	Mining Land (Pits, Tailings Dams, etc.)	High-resolution vector	Maus et al. (2020)	A global mining land use dataset created via remote sensing analysis of high-resolution, publicly available satellite imagery, covering mining-related features.
Gridfinder	Electricity Network	Low Voltage is as raster, others as vector	Christopher Arderne, Conrad Zorn, Claire Nicolas, Elco Koks	A tool for predicting the location of electricity network lines using night-time lights satellite imagery and OpenStreetMap data.
OSM	Various Critical Infrastructures	Vector format	OSM Community	A harmonized spatial dataset for representing critical infrastructure globally using OpenStreetMap data.
Electricity + plant network (PyPSA) - including network and power stations above 220kV	Electricity Network	Vector format	Py-PSA EUROPE	PyPSA-Eur: A Sector-Coupled Open Optimisation Model of the European Energy System
Power plants – installed capacity in MW (JRC)	Electricity Network	Vector format - NUTS2	JRC-PPDB	
Electricity network (SciGRID Power - various datasets)	Electricity Network	Vector format	SCIGRID-Power Consortium	
Gas network (Various datasets)	Electricity Network	Vector format	SCIGRID-Gas Consortium	
Facilities of the energy-intensive industries (combined ETS and E-PRTR data)	Electricity Network	Vector format	EEA	This includes a lot of production facilities for cement, oil, and other pollution sources
Broadband and Mobile Network speeds	Telecommunications	18 arcsecond blocks	Ookla	Speedtest data is used today by commercial fixed and mobile network operators around the world to inform network buildout, improve global Internet quality, and increase Internet accessibility.

Solar, Wind, Biomass	Energy Potentials	NUTS2	Ruiz et al., 2019	an open data, EU-28 wide, transparent and coherent database of wind, solar and biomass energy potentials
CO2 and greenhouse emissions	Emissions data	Gridmaps etc.	EDGAR consortium	EDGARv8.0 is the second product of the new EDGAR Community GHG emissions database, which is the outcome of an agreement between JRC and IEA to work more closely to gather and provide consistent harmonised CO2 emissions from fossil fuel combustion.
Global ML Roads Dataset	Global Road Network	Vector	GEE	<i>This has not been sourced yet owing to the fact is only available to the Insiders Program but should be mentioned here.</i>
Mining Footprints	Mine footprints	Vector	Tang and Werner (2023)	A global set of mining footprints - which has been extracted for Europe
GISCO Transport Data	Airports and Ports (year 2013)	Vector	EC	A European dataset of port and airport details.

Table 23: Overview of available landcover and agriculture exposure datasets.

Data Set/Model	Asset type	Resolution	Author(s)	Description
Agricultural GDP	Agriculture (livestock, crop, fishery, forestry, hunting)	5 arc-minutes (~10x10km)	Ru et al. (2023)	Global gridded dataset of disaggregated national and subnational administrative statistics of agricultural GDP for the year 2010 based on satellite-derived indicators of the components that make up agricultural GDP, i.e., crop, livestock, fishery, hunting and forestry production.
Fishing GDP	Fishery	5 arc-minutes (~10x10km)	Ru et al. (2023)	Global gridded dataset of fish production value (freshwater inland fisheries and marine production) for the year 2010.
Livestock production value	Livestock	5 arc-minutes (~10x10km)	Ru et al. (2023)	Global gridded dataset of livestock production value based on distribution maps of five primary species and FAOSTAT's value of production of livestock products (including milk, meat, eggs, wool, and honey).
Gridded Livestock of the World (GLW)	Livestock	5 arc-minutes (~10x10km)	FAO's Livestock Information, Sector Analysis and Policy Branch (NSAL)	Global spatial dataset on the distribution and abundance of different livestock species (buffaloes, cattle, chicken, ducks, goats, horses, pigs and sheep)
CORINE Land Cover (CLC)	Land Cover, Infrastructure	Vector and 100m raster	European Environment Agency	Provides information on the land cover of Europe (44 thematic classes) for environmental assessment purposes, updated every six years.
GHS-SMOD	Settlement types	1km raster	European Commission, JRC	Multitemporal Global Human Settlement layer (1975-2030) with settlement type information.
GHS-BUILT-C MSZ	Open Spaces (vegetation, water, road), built spaces (residential and non-residential)	10m raster	European Commission, JRC	Global Human Settlement layer that delineates human settlements and describes the built environment and the functional use.
GHS-SDATA-E2018-S2MAXNDVI	NDVI	10m raster	European Commission, JRC	Global Human Settlement layer that reports the maximum NDVI collected from Sentinel-2 images in 2018.
WSF	Settlement Areas	10m raster	German Aerospace Center (DLR)	Making use of both radar and optical imagery at the same time this dataset outlines the extent of human settlements globally.
ESA WorldCover	Land Cover	10m raster	European Space Agency (ESA)	Global land cover product containing eleven land cover classes based on both Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-1 data.
Global Land Cover - SHARE (GLC-SHARE)	Land Cover	30 arc-seconds (~1x1km)	Land and Water Division of FAO	Global land cover database that provides a set of eleven major thematic land cover layers based on contributions from various institutions by a combination of "best available" high resolution national, sub-national and/or

GlobeLand 30	Land Cover	30m raster	National Geomatics Center of China (NGCC)	regional land cover databases. The first 30m resolution global land cover dataset, comprising ten different types of land cover for the years 2000 and 2010 based on more than 20,000 Landsat and Chinese HJ-1 satellite images.
PROBA-V Global Land Cover	Land Cover, Forest Type	100m raster	Copernicus Global Land Service (CGLS)	Collection of 100m land cover products for the years 2015-2019 derived from PROBA-V satellite observations, including a main discrete classification with 23 classes, a forest type layer and a set of versatile cover fraction for ten main classes.
EFFIS Fuel Map	Fuel Type	250m raster	European Commission, JRC	European-level dataset which initially maps 42 fuel types that are organised in 9 groups, further converted into the 13 fuel models of the National Fire Danger Rating System (NFDRS) of which only 10 are used to assess wildfire behaviour.

Figure 29: Map of forest cover (closed timber litter) per cell based on the EFFIS database.

Appendix B: Hazard Examples from the datasets

Figure 30: Comparison of dataset outputs (single, probabilistic, stochastic) for earthquake hazards. Upper: Created shakemap for the 2023 Turkey event; Middle: SHARE-EU Probabilistic map at 4975 year return period, Lower: Stochastic event set built from SERA-EU for 100 years.

Figure 31: Tsunami event for the 365AD Hellenic Arc Earthquake.

Figure 32: Comparison of dataset outputs (single, probabilistic, stochastic) for wind hazards: Upper: WISC, Middle: RAIN, Lower: PRIMAVERA.

Single event / historical

Probabilistic

Figure 33: Comparison of dataset outputs (single, probabilistic) for flood hazards: Upper: (Amalgamation of HANZE, DFO, CATDAT), Middle: JRC, Lower: PIK Stochastic Danube Set with future scenarios sourced for use in MYRIAD-EU.

Figure 34: Comparison of dataset outputs (single, probabilistic) for landslide hazards - Upper: Global Landslide Catalog, Lower: ELSUS v2 Landslide Susceptibility.

Figure 35: Comparison of dataset outputs for tornado hazards - Upper: RAIN probabilistic set presenting annual probability of occurrence, Lower: ESWD tornadoes and their strength.

Figure 36: Hail event frequency as estimated by Punge et al. (2014).